

Vertical Innovations in Transport And Logistics over 5G experimentation facilities

D3.1 Report on VITAL-5G infrastructure upgrades & extensions

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Glossary of terms and abbreviations used

Abbreviation / Term	Description
3GPP	3rd Generation Partnership Project
3PL	third-party Logistics
4G	fourth generation network
5G	fifth generation network
5G-IA	5G Infrastructure Association
5G-PPP	5G Infrastructure Public Private Partnership
5GC	5G Core
AGV	Automated Guided Vehicle
AI	Artificial Intelligence
AIS	Automatic Identification System
API	Application Programming Interface
APICS	Antwerp Port Information and Control System
AR	Augmented reality
BSS	Business Support System
CaaS	Container as a Service
CAN	Controller Area Network
CI/CD	Continuous Integration/Continuous Delivery
CM	Configuration Management
CNF	Cloud-native Network Functions
CPE	Customer Premises Equipment
DC	Data Center
DL	Down Link
DN	Data Network
DRB	Data Radio Bearer
DSS	Dynamic Spectrum Sharing
DVR	Digital Video Recorder
DMZ	Demilitarized Zone
ENISA	European Union Agency for Cybersecurity
E2E	End to End

ECM	Evolved Packet System Connection Management
EVPN	Ethernet VPN
EM	Element Manager
eMBB	Enhanced Mobile Broadband
eMBC	Enhanced Mobile Broadband Communications
eNB	evolved Node B
ETA	Estimated Time of Arrival
ETSI	European Telecommunications Standards Institute
FEFO	First Expired, First Out
FIFO	First In, First Out
FR1	Frequency Range 1
FR2	Frequency Range 2
FM	Fault Management
GIS	Geographic Information System
gNB	Next Generation Node B
GNSS	Global Navigation Satellite System
GPS	Global Positioning System
GUI	Graphical User Interface
HD	High Definition
HDD	Hard Digital Disk
HW	Hardware
IaaS	Infrastructure as a service
ICE	Inland, Coastal & Estuary
IoT	Internet of Things
IP	Internet Protocol
JSON	JavaScript Object Notation
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
L2	Layer 2
L3	Layer 3
LAN	Local Area Network
LCM	Lifecycle Management

LIDAR	Light Detection And Ranging
MANO	Management and Orchestration
MEC	Multi-access Edge Computing
MF	Management Functions
MIMO	Multiple Input Multiple Output
ML	Machine Learning
mMTC	massive Machine Type Communications
MNO	Mobile Network Operator
MPLS	Multiprotocol Label Switching
MS	Management Functions
MQTT	Message Queuing Telemetry Transport
NBI	Northbound Interface
NF	Network Function
NFV	Network Function Virtualization
NFVO	Network Function Virtualization Orchestration
NR	New Radio
NSA	Non-Stand Alone
NSSAI	Network Slice Selection Assistance Information
NST	Network Slice Template
NVR	Network Video Recorder
OBD	On-Board Diagnostics
OBU	On-Board Units
ONAP	Open Network Automation Platform
OSM	Open Source Management and Orchestration
OSS	Operations Support System
PDN	Packet Data Network
PDU	Packet Data Unit
PLC	Programmable Logic Controller
PLMN	Public Land Mobile Network
PMR	Private Mobile Radio
PNF	Physical Network Functions

PPDR	Public Protection & Disaster Relief
PoA	Port of Antwerp
QoE	Quality of Experience
QoS	Quality of Service
RAN	Radio Access Network
RL	Reinforcement Learning
RPM	Revolutions per Minute
S-NSSAI	Single Network Slice Selection Assistance Information
SA	Stand Alone
SBA	Service Based Architecture
SBI	South-bound Interface
SCC	Shore Control Centers
SD	Service Differentiator
SDN	Software Defined Network
SDO	Standards Developing Organization
SIM	Subscriber Identity Module
SLA	Service Level Agreement
SR	Segment Routing
SW	Software
T&L	Transport & Logistics
TEN-T	Trans-European Transport Network
TOS	Terminal Operating System
UC	Use Case
UE	User Equipment
UL	Up Link
URLLC	Ultra-Reliable and Low Latency Communications
USB	Universal Serial Bus
V2X	Vehicle-to-Everything
VA	Vertical-Agnostic Network Application
vCPU	virtual Central Processing Unit
vEPC	virtual Evolved Packet Core
VIM	Virtualized Infrastructure Manager

VHF	Very High Frequency
VNF	Virtual Network Function
VR	Virtual Reality
VS	Vertical-Specific Network Application
VxLAN	Virtual Extensible LAN
WDM	Wavelength-division multiplexing
VSAT	Very small aperture terminal
WMS	Warehouse Management System

Executive Summary

This deliverable presents in detail the testbeds upgrade activities and integration steps performed in the VITAL-5G project to enable the realisation of three distributed European 5G-testbeds and associated vertical infrastructures for the execution of advanced Transport & Logistics (T&L) experiments. The proposed design is expected to support several key project objectives, including the *Objective 2*, by delivering the open, virtualized 5G-enabled testing and validation experimentation facilities.

The end-to-end 5G network and facility framework has been created supporting the development and testing of the Network Applications for T&L sector, demonstrating from a technical perspective the benefits and showcasing the added value provided by 5G connectivity.

The VITAL-5G reference architecture is proposed a blueprint approach to build a 5G system that will be Rel.16 compliant, providing a detailed view of the **key relevant components** and **functionalities**. The main 5G system components are analysed in detail, identifying the extensions and upgrades required for existing infrastructures, as far as **RAN** and **Core, Orchestration** and **Automation, Slicing** concepts and **Security** are concerned.

One of the main requirements of the project is to deliver three 5G testbeds that are 3GPP Rel.16 compliant, to take advantage of the novel technology's developments and capabilities. In order to make clear the architecture alignment with the existing standards and related work, in this deliverable we perform a deep analysis of different Standardization Bodies (e.g., **ETSI, 3GPP**), the **5G-PPP** (5G Infrastructure Public Private Partnership) overall architecture and achievements in terms of 5G integration and implementation, including other **5G-PPP projects results**. The mandatory 5G features and capabilities are defined, by benchmarking and providing comparison with the available features in the testbeds. Furthermore, the needed network upgrades and integrations for the key network and platform domains of VITAL-5G Platform and VITAL-5G testbeds are detailed.

Beyond the 5G infrastructure layers, Management and Orchestration, 5G monitoring systems, **the slicing concepts** are presented in detail, from the theoretical perspective to the final 5G SA slices implementation in the testbeds. In fact, the project consortium has defined an innovative way of service's slice deployment, multi-slice available testbeds consumed by T&L parties.

The deliverable also presents the three VITAL-5G facilities' existing capabilities, concluding the required upgrades and integration activities, in order to answer to the 5G use cases related requirements. The 5G testbeds implementation plan is described in the deliverable, highlighting the main steps of 5G infrastructure integration, focusing on Rel.16 capabilities.

We have aligned with the overall **5G-PPP architecture** and related efforts, as a proper 5G integration and deployment guide from the architecture and standardization perspective, state-of-the-art 5G-testbeds, functions and capabilities of the testbeds, to the 5G network implementations and integrations required. An analysis is also presented regarding the activities performed in the project and what has been used from other/ past research activities, thus concluding what the effort of the VITAL-5G project is to perform the upgrades and integrations, so as all three testbeds can be developed to support Network Application requirements, as a unitary method of implementation.

One of the requirements was to implement from the beginning the **security aspects** in VITAL-5G, clearly defined as a **5G security approach (testbeds and platform)**, from two main perspectives: (1) the 5G SA security, by following the **SA3 security implementation**, protocols and rules and, (2) security provided by the VITAL-5G for the **testbeds and Centralized platform**, by implementing the **latest security technologies** as Firewalls, DDoS system, cybersecurity reports, active monitoring of the entire system, rules of access provided by design and testbeds and platform secured access for developers and 3rd parties (users,

passwords exchanged secured, encryption). It has been extended to the level of the virtualized infrastructure, implementing security concepts as **DMZ** or Demilitarized Zone, as a physical or logical network that contains and exposes VITAL-5G external-facing services to outside domains through isolation, as an additional layer of security by creating a buffer zone. In VITAL-5G, the **DMZ** is the common implemented security measure in the design to protect the Platform and the testbeds for external threats, thus by monitoring with security professional tools the threats are mitigated. In this context, the security is defined and is a relevant component in the **VITAL-5G E2E** architecture.

By **December 2022** all the three testbeds have been upgraded and aligned with the target architecture, for RAN, Core, Virtualization and Orchestration, requested upgrades and extensions being performed, testbeds and platform components being integrated and validated from a functionality perspective. Project's Network Application are also already onboarded as presented in D3.2 [69], as the applications are deployed through the VITAL-5G platform, within a High Available 5G network environment.

1 Introduction

VITAL-5G is proposing an advanced 5G architecture of the three testbeds for Network Application validation and experiments, presenting the entire vision as the complex network infrastructure combined with the vertical specialized facilities capabilities. One of the project objectives is to provide an open **Service Platform** (VITAL-5G Platform) which through Application Programming Interfaces (APIs), as secured interfaces, there will be interconnected with the three 5G testbeds (Mobile Network Operators - MNOs) and, in collaboration with the vertical's infrastructures, creating the opportunity to validate the T&L (Transport & Logistics) solutions and services. The scenario of validation is performed in the real-life testbeds' resources environment and the targeted facilities are making available the proper tools and 5G technologies to achieve the demanding experiments' requirements. The 5G testbeds support the experimentation platform by guaranteeing the technology deployment of the advanced networks and techniques for E2E services deployment and SLA/KPIs assurance, i.e., 5G communication services implementation for Enhanced Mobile Broadband (eMBB), Ultra-Reliable and Low Latency Communications (URLLC), massive Machine Type Communications (mMTC). Also, a key aspect, the **E2E network slicing implementation** allows for dynamic and flexible services support, as a high degree of automation and coordination within and across network domains is required.

In this deliverable the testbed's architecture design is highly important, together with the upgrades and integrations in line with the standards, 5G-PPP efforts and targeting 3GPP Rel.16 capabilities, while keeping the focus on the main project *Objectives*, and specifically *Objective 2* - to deliver an open, virtualized 5G-enabled testing and validation experimentation facility with the Network Application running on top of the 5G network. Upgrades and testbeds extensions have been evaluated and integrated in the proposed architecture for the new services orchestration platform and VITAL-5G Platform, including advanced features such as network slicing and service orchestration, VNF onboarding, Life-Cycle Management (LCM), performance diagnostics and abstract experiment specification through intent-based mechanisms. Moreover, the three testbeds are individually implemented, connected through APIs to the Centralized Platform, for Network Application onboarding, deployment, testing and experimentation and monitoring.

The deliverable provides a clear view of the 3GPP Rel.16 required characteristics, translated into a 5G SA implementation plan of the testbeds, with respect of 5G SA slicing concepts, security and 3rd party access to the testbed for experimentation.

1.1 Mapping VITAL-5G Outputs

The purpose of this section is to map VITAL-5G's Grant Agreement commitments, both within the formal Deliverable and Task description, against the project's respective outputs and work performed.

Table 1: Adherence to VITAL-5G's GA Deliverable & Tasks Descriptions

GA Component Title	GA Component Outline	Respective Document Chapter(s)	Justification
TASKS			
Task 3.1 VITAL-5G infrastructure upgrades & extensions	5G-PPP overall architecture overview and analysis of main standards and implementation	Section 2	In this section we are focusing on Rel.16 RAN/Core features, 5G network evolution to the 5G SA target architecture, slicing definition, virtualization and

(Covered D3.1)			orchestration aspects, E2E service deployment, tools available and advanced monitoring systems.
	VITAL 5G state-of-the-art of the three testbeds	Section 3	In this section we are describing existing capabilities and resources and the 1 st stage of the 5G NSA/SA network implementation with the description of further needs of network testbeds' software and hardware upgrades. This section is defining the basic initial setup of the testbeds and infrastructure.
	VITAL-5G E2E facility reference architecture	Section 4	In this section the overall facility concept has been defined with the envisioned 5G architecture and interfaces of an open 5G distributed testbed. The 5G system and network resources and features set of the testbeds have been created, containing the required 5G network elements, hardware and software components, for 5G RAN, Core, and EDGE computing implementation. This section is presenting in fact the foundation of VITAL-5G target architecture.
	Security/cyber security concerns related to the 5G networks	Section 5	In this section we are explaining the 5G Network perspective (RAN/Core/Virtualization) for the VITAL-5G security implementation of the different scenarios such as the platform deployment, testbed's interfaces to the platform, developers and Network Application access and securely hosting in the virtualized infrastructure.
	Required upgrades/extensions to deliver 5G-testbeds that are Rel.16 compliant	Section 6	In this section we are presenting software and hardware network upgrades, integration of the new components, network slices implementation in the testbeds and orchestration in the VITAL-5G

		<p>facility. The presented implementation concepts are similar for each of the three testbeds in the project. It is evaluated, based on the target architecture, testbeds available 5G resources in terms of capacity, network slices, virtual resources that can be consumed by the Network Applications.</p>
DELIVERABLE		
<p>D3.1 Report on VITAL-5G infrastructure upgrades & extensions</p> <p>Report on the VITAL-5G testbed and infrastructure upgrades and extensions, including early components integration results.</p>		

1.2 Deliverable Overview and Report Structure

One of the primary goals of this report is to define and implement all the 5G testbeds software, hardware upgrades and extensions of the existing clusters, to deliver the 5G RAN/Core functionality to the Network Application experimenters, highlighting also the major role played by the 5G technology within the vertical’s use cases context. More specifically, the document is structured in several sections as follows:

- Section 2 gives a technological standards 5G-PPP/3GPP architecture definition, as a proposed framework of 5G requirements, features and capabilities, the motivation supporting the 5G efforts and deployments, key features and major network components overview;
- Section 3, apart from presenting the state-of-the-art of each one of the testbeds, evaluates the 5G testbeds and 5G capabilities, from which it will be built the 5G E2E testbeds architecture;
- Section 4 is providing the VITAL-5G testbeds reference architecture, the VITAL-5G approach and blueprint for designing and building the 5G system, providing a comprehensive overview of the testbeds to platform interfaces;
- Section 5 focuses on the 5G security requirements, from the 3GPP perspective, supported by existing standards and security/cyber-security recommendations, but also provides the project overview and proposed design for the project implementation, including platform/testbeds access for the Network Application developers and 3rd party experimenters. It presents the project perspective and implementation of security concepts in VITAL-5G;
- Section 6 translates all the 5G architectural concepts described into the practical implementation activities of the testbeds, seen as a complex E2E activity for which there have been identified risks of delays and mitigations actions;
- Section 7 is analyzing the possible risks related to several aspects as hardware and software deliver and mitigations actions for proper testbeds infrastructure delivery;
- Finally, Section 8 presents the Conclusions, highlighting the overall results of this report, targeted objectives for the infrastructures upgrades and extensions to the target architecture, and also provides an output for the next project deliverables.

2 Overall architecture from standardization

This chapter aims to describe the general 5G-PPP architecture, the evolution towards 3GPP (3rd Generation Partnership Project) Rel. 16 and to highlight the main components (RAN, CORE, etc.). It defines the baseline of the technology achievements, the relevant standards and the mapping between the SDOs (Standards Developing Organization) and other 5G-PPP efforts with respect to VITAL-5G required upgrades and integrations.

5G is the key enabler for new business and for digital transformation initiatives to integrate vertical automotive, energy, manufacturing, entertainment industries into the network slice concept. It focuses on maximizing the sharing of network resources and creating dedicated logical networks with personalized customer specific functions. 5G architecture, as defined by 5G-PPP [1] efforts and involvement, aims to support the vertical industries and the service performance in the 5G-PPP ecosystem over different experimental 5G facilities.

Several architectural considerations and aspects are considered in order to support the 5G vertical's requirements, addressed by different Network Applications, and there are several types of network slices described by 3GPP, i.e., eMBB, URLLC, mMTC and V2X (Vehicle-to-Everything) services. The facilities extensions and capabilities needed to be implemented and several key factors are listed below:

1. **Service layer evolution:** 5G vertical's APIs integration, NBIs (Northbound Interfaces) and functions exposure for SA deployments;
2. **Service performance assurance** tools [2]: evaluation of overall performance of the service layer and of the relevant key performance indicators, service layer information;
3. **EDGE/MEC (Multi-access Edge Computing)** [4] capabilities and orchestration: introduced in 5G networks, for delivering computing capabilities close to the data sources, in order to improve the performance, costs and application reliability;
4. **Secured architecture for 5G networks:** protection of the network and system assets, services, data and network infrastructures against potential security/cybersecurity risks;
5. **End-to-end service network slicing** enhanced slice management, scalability;
6. **Virtualization** and telco-oriented **orchestration** and LCM, ETSI (European Telecommunications Standards Institute) MANO (Management and Orchestration) NFVs, cloud native orchestration containers and Kubernetes(K8S), AI (Artificial Intelligence) based orchestration;
7. **Test cases** and **experiments** execution capabilities for vertical's validation processes, support for sandbox and trials, network architecture validation;
8. 5G **RAN** and **Core** advanced architectures: services discovery in the SBA (Service Based Architecture) enabled architectures, adoption of cloudification principles;
9. **Monitoring framework:** tracing and analysis of logs, visualization of metrics and test reports;
10. **Transport network** and backhaul orchestration.

These objectives have also been addressed, to a certain extent, in other projects and steps have been made towards standardization. As described by [6] the 5G-IA Pre-Standardization Working Group launched a survey aimed at analyzing the impact on standardization reached by 5G-PPP Horizon 2020 active projects. Its goal was to identify the achieved and planned impact of these projects on 5G standards and the areas of improvement for maximizing the research results transfer to standardization bodies for future research frameworks (e.g., Horizon Europe).

E2E Service Operations functions interact with management of domain resources and functions that include RAN, Core & Transport Network, NFV and MEC as presented in Figure 1. To manage these interactions, closed-loop procedures are developed for resource fulfilment, resource assurance, and network intelligence comprise building blocks within each management domain.

Network programmability is also one of the key concepts of the 5G network, ensuring the end-to-end orchestration through a flexible configuration of the control plane and data plane (data plane programmability) of the transport network, SDN exploitation.

Figure 1: 5G-PPP Overall Architecture [1]

5G Rel. 16 [7] system enhancements (5GS) are enabling several vertical industries, mentioning different business areas: autonomous driving V2X, railways, maritime, automated factories, healthcare, public safety, electrical power distribution, satellite industrial domain, logistics and transportation. 5GS improvements are supported by the 5G technology strengthening and are reflected through the new network services with enhancements to URLLC, network slicing, edge computing, mMTC and industrial IoT (Industry 4.0), positioning services, described by Figure 2.

Figure 2: Release 16 5G features and enhancements supporting verticals [1]

RAN/Cloud RAN

Advanced 5G radio architecture concepts support NR (New Radio) in new spectrum (unlicensed and mm wave, FR1 (Frequency Range 1) and FR2 (Frequency Range 2)), Industrial IoT and ultra-reliable and low-latency communication, multi-radio dual connectivity, Carrier-Aggregation, massive-MIMO (Multiple Input Multiple Output), DSS (Dynamic Spectrum Sharing), QoE and RAN optimization services, RAN network slicing, higher positioning accuracy, dynamic network control, redundant transmission paths for ultra-reliable communication (failure avoidance). As described by 3GPP new features are implemented, such as RAN QoS monitoring, intra and inter-slice RAN scheduling and resources prioritization, packet control delay and PDPC packet multiplication. Another important enhancement is the open RAN and vRAN deployment, which is a flexible, scalable and multi-vendor interoperable solution to run the radio baseband functions as software within NFV/VNFs framework.

5GCN

The 5G core system will efficiently cater for applications which have variable requirements relating to specific QoS parameters (e.g., throughput). It will also cater for applications which are able to adapt to a range of variations in QoS. The 5G Core system will enable the user of a single terminal to establish and maintain several connections simultaneously. It will be possible for a user to be associated with one or a number of user profiles to be active simultaneously and have a subscription-based access which describes the commercial relationship between the subscriber and the service provider. 5G Core systems must support stringent KPIs for latency, reliability, throughput, enhancements in the core network, such as network slicing, in-network caching and hosting services closer to the end points, MEC, ultra-reliable and low latency communication.

Network slicing

Network slicing refers to the concept of creating logical networks with appropriate isolation, resources and optimized topology to serve a purpose or service category (e.g., use case/traffic category, or for MNO

internal reasons) or customers (logical system created "on demand"). The network slice provides specific network capabilities, characterized by certain properties as radio access technology, bandwidth, end-to-end latency, reliability, guaranteed QoS, security level through a set of Network Functions (SBA) instances and consuming the required resources as compute, storage and networking, ensuring the end-to-end communication performance.

Figure 3: Slice Concept evolution to 5G

Network slicing implies multiple logical mobile network instances executions on a shared infrastructure with continuous reconciliation of service QoS demands with infrastructure-level network performance capabilities. There are different options to implemented slicing, based on 3GPP specifications, as seen in Figure 3: a) slicing based on APN configuration, core network support for slicing requirements, b) DÉCOR implementation, core network selection through HSS and c) 5G slicing, the slice selection being performed based on S-NSSAI, implementation support in RAN, core and device. In VITAL-5G the slicing implementation is option c, network slice selection described in Figure 4.

Figure 4: 5G network slice selection

Previous generation supported certain aspects of this with the functionality for dedicated Core Networks. 5G network slicing is a more powerful concept and includes the whole PLMN (Public Land Mobile Network), as described in Figure 3 and the 5G network slices are selected by the proper network slice parameters, the S-NSSAI (Single Network Slice Selection Assistance Information) at the UE level, requiring support at UE, 5GCN and RAN level and offering simultaneously connectivity to different PDNs (Packet Data Networks). Within this, there are defined slice groups (NSSAI) containing single slice identification(S-NSSAI), as the S-NSSAI contains the slice template (SST) as can be seen in Figure 4 and the service/slice

descriptor (SD), for which there are already pre-defined SST standardized values. A NSSAI is a collection of S-NSSAIs (max 8), as a given PDU session belongs to only one specific slice, but a UE can be served by up to 8 slices simultaneously, as the main parameters for proper slicing are (1) Subscribed NSSAI, (2) Configured NSSAI, (3) Allowed NSSAI and (4) Requested NSSAI.

Table 2: 5G Service slice standardized values

Slice/Service type	SST value	Characteristics
eMBB	1	Slice suitable for the handling of 5G enhanced Mobile Broadband
URLLC	2	Slice suitable for the handling of ultra-reliable low latency communication
mMTC	3	Slice suitable for the handling of massive IoT

An E2E network slicing includes slicing support on RAN, core and transport. Each IP flow from use case applications can be identified and secured in QoS flow and resulted in different DRB (Data Radio Bearer) mappings as shown in Figure 5 below:

Figure 5: 5G network slicing: IP flow, QoS flow and DRB mapping

EDGE/MEC

EDGE computing is enabling services to be hosted close to the UE's access point of attachment, efficient service delivery through the reduced end-to-end latency and network load, unlocking the value of IoT, 5G, AR/VR, video, AI, analytics and cloud. Edge computing is an architecture leveraging cloud capabilities that locates processing power and storage closer to the source of data generation, seen as a network evolution to EDGE Computing as shown in Figure 6.

Figure 6: 5G EDGE computing

EDGE computing facility implementation is depending on each use case requirements, as there is no implementation that fits all.

2.1 5G-PPP supporting projects and clusters

The 5G features and capabilities are technically sustained by the virtualized, software-based network functions, cloud-native applications and orchestration tools, automatic deployment and instantiation of different NFVs/VNFs, lifecycle management (LCM) tools for the software functions, horizontal and vertical scaling. These initial concepts of Network Slicing, 5G RAN and Core reference architecture or virtualized environment deployment and orchestration have been presented in different 5G-PPP projects such as 5G-EVE [8], 5G-VICTORI [9], 5G-BLUEPRINT [10], 5GASP[11].

2.1.1 5G-EVE

5G-EVE [8] is the 5G European validation platform for 5G vertical trials to offer support for roll-out of end-to-end 5G networks in Europe, heterogeneous access, including NR, licensed/unlicensed spectrum, advanced spectrum management; Mobile Edge Computing, backhaul, core/service technologies; site-interworking and multi-site/domain/technology slicing/orchestration. Industrial verticals are facilitated in the specification/analysis of experiments through intent-based and other high-level interfaces for advanced 5G testing, KPI analysis, technology benchmarking, performance diagnosis.

2.1.2 5G-VICTORI

5G-VICTORI [9] is a 5G-PPP project phase III whose purpose is to integrate commercially relevant, operational environments required for the demonstration of the large variety of vertical and cross-vertical use cases. An example of a 5G-EVE [8] supported project is the 5G-VICTORI France/Romania cluster addressing two vertical use cases proposed for transportation and energy demonstrated in Romania supported by technologies as OpenStack for VIM, OSM or ONAP, and Kubernetes.

2.1.3 5G-BLUEPRINT

The overall objective of the 5G-Blueprint [10] project is to design and validate a technical architecture, business model and governance model for uninterrupted cross-border teleoperated transport based on 5G connectivity. 5G-Blueprint is very relevant to the VITAL-5G work as the two projects share the 5G

infrastructure used in the port of Antwerp, which will be upgraded to Rel.16 SA for the completion of the VITAL-5G trials. The common partners shared among the two projects, namely IMEC, TEL and SF, will guarantee the knowledge transfer from 5G-Blueprint and will capitalize on lessons learned in order to more effectively set-up the VITAL-5G trials and to maximize the reuse of components.

2.1.4 5GASP

5GASP [11] project aims to shorten the idea-to-market process through the creation of a European Network Application deployment, testing and certification ecosystem primarily developed for SMEs and start-ups, that is fully automated and self-service, in order to foster rapid development and testing of innovative Network Application built using the 5G NFV based reference architecture. To that extent, 5GASP focuses on inter-domain use-cases [12] (e.g., Automotive, cooperative mobility and PPDR), development of operational tools and procedures (supporting day-to-day testing and validation activities) and security/trust of 3rd party Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) running in our testbeds.

2.2 5G Network Infrastructure

The 5G system consists of a 5G core network (5GC) and a 5G radio access network (NG-RAN). 5GC itself, comprises functional components, AMF for access and mobility management function, UPF for user plane functions and SMF for session management functions.

2.2.1 RAN

5G New Radio (NR) [13] is built on several new enhancements: a new spectrum, Massive MIMO and beamforming, physical layer numerology, multi-connectivity and virtualization. Massive MIMO improves capacity, coverage, spectrum efficiency and is necessary to suppress inter-cell interference. Beamforming, while used in LTE, becomes especially important in 5G and is dynamic, steerable and switchable.

Regarding the RAN architecture, the Option 3x nodes are connected with each other by means of a X2 interface, a logical interface that can be split into a X2-U for the user plane data supporting PDU, GTP-U, UDP, IP and X2-C for the control plane data supporting X2-AP, SCTP, IP and data link protocols. The gNB can be divided between the centralized unit and distributed unit. The gNB and eNB are connected to the 4G core network via the S1 interface, as depicted in Figure 7.

Figure 7: 5G SA/NSA implementation options a) Option 2 and b) Option 3x

In 5G SA Option 2, the RAN consists of only gNBs that are connected to the 5G Core network. The gNB connects to AMF over NG-C interface for control plane signaling and it connects to UPF over NG-U interface for user plane data transfer. gNBs are connected to each other via Xn interface. gNB provides the NR (New Radio) air interface access to the UEs. The 5G SA Option 2 [14] architecture does not have any impact on the LTE network and it supports all the 5G use cases defined by 3GPP.

The RAN includes the Service Data Adaptation Protocol layer and the F1 interface with Centralized Unit – Distributed Unit split as presented in Figure 8. This innovative architecture provides Small Cell coverage to multiple operators “as-a-Service” and uses virtualization techniques for data isolation, latency reduction and resource efficiency. By employing orchestration of lightweight virtual resources enabling efficient Virtualized Network Function (VNF) placement and live migration, it can support small cell capacity as well as enhanced edge cloud services, by enriching the network infrastructure with an edge cloud.

Figure 8: CU/DU RAN Architecture for enhanced network performance

One of the key functions of 5G RAN to support network slicing is priority management with 5G QoS Flow input, UE TCP session, and 5G QoS Flow to DRB mapping. The network first maps different IP flows with same QoS requirements into the same QoS Flow, as illustrated in Figure 5. For non-guaranteed bit rate flows (non-GBR) the total bandwidth is limited by the aggregated maximum bit rate (AMBR) which is similar to the 4G network. The gNB maps QoS Flows into different DRB parameter as defined in [15].

2.2.2 Core infrastructure and functionalities

The 5G architecture is an evolution of the 4G architecture that introduces major changes such as the Service Based Architecture (SBA). In an SBA, as defined in 3GPP, the primary architectural components that are put forward are services, which are used to execute different sets of functions with authorization to access each other’s services. These interconnected network functions (NFs) foresee the control plane functionality and common data repositories of a 5G network. The transition to SBA separates the end-user service from the underlying network. The Service Based Architecture for core 5G networks is defined in [15]. Many of the advanced features of 5G including network function virtualization and network slicing for different applications and services, will be managed in the core, deployed as SBA, as shown in Figure 9.

In Release 16 the 5G system architecture [15] is enriched with two additional network functions:

- **NSSAAF** - Network Slice Specific Authentication and Authorization Function providing the authentication and authorization functionality at slice level;

- SCP** - Service Communication Proxy used for the communication between consumer functions and provider functions, as described in Figure 10, 5GC service-based architecture [14] is based on a set of functions providing services to other authorized network functions via service-based interfaces using the Network Repository Function. All these interfaces are standardized and open. Also, the notion of Service Consumer and Service Provider are related to the 5GC in the cloud native ecosystem supporting containerization and micro services.

Figure 9: 5GC service-based architecture

Figure 10: 5G SA Service requests flows

2.2.3 Multi-Access Edge Computing

Multi-Access Edge Computing (MEC) offers applications and content providers computing capabilities at the network edge, for a series of services, as described in Figure 11.

The MEC system reference architecture is deployed in an NFV environment as VNFs towards ETSI MANO NFV components. The virtualized infrastructure is deployed as NFVI and managed as VIM and the VNFs life cycle management is provided by the platform management and platform orchestrator components. When an application needs more resources, the cloud automatically spins up another instance of that application and removes an instance when load decreases. Such flexible scaling is impossible to achieve when the application is implemented with dedicated hardware.

Figure 11: Multi-Access Edge Computing (MEC) implementation

2.2.4 Transport network layer

RAN transport interaction introduces coordination between the radio, transport and packet core layers of an operator’s mobile network as presented in Figure 12, providing network-wide optimization and service assurance. Examples of such coordination include:

- Transport architecture [17] for 5G SBA services, ring or mesh deployment for access fronthaul, aggregation middle-haul and core backhaul.
- Network resource differentiation into the transport for supporting of various industries, connectivity provided through radio microwaves, optical (WDMs) or L2/L3(advanced routing, SR MPLS, VXLAN, EPVN) communication network.
- Proactive congestion management, enabling transport aware-RAN load balancing for improved user QoE, enabling separation of control/user plane entities and disaggregating the RAN functionalities.
- Automatic end-users services provisioning, optimization and service KPIs assurance.
- Programmable and elastic network, both optical and L2/L3 network, transport network slicing.

Figure 12: 5G transport architecture

2.2.5 5G Virtualization environment

Virtualization is one of the key requirements components for 5G network deployment, as the 5G system is mainly based on virtualized network solutions, supporting the 5G SBA deployment, the modularized services, flexible and adaptable, on-demand networks, fast deployment cycles, and dynamic services launched in the network. In 5G networks, due to virtualization of the network, the functions may be instantiated, terminated, configured, scale in/out and updated more rapidly than traditional physical implementations, to support the on-demand communication service instantiation, also including the network slicing.

Figure 13: Evolution of the VNFs toward Cloud Native network functions

We see an evolution from the past MANO-centric, decoupling the software from hardware, NFV/VNFs solution towards cloud-native, even if for a period there will be a coexistence of traditional VNFs and containers to future Kubernetes centric CNFs [18].

2.3 Management services and Orchestration Layer

A network wide orchestration for 5G services aims at deploying the network functions dynamically and automatically programming the connectivity network paths between different components. It also replaces the traditional methods of network configuration, manually configured individual boxes and layers, by using the industry management and orchestration tools in a coordinated way.

The management service offers management capabilities that are accessed by the service consumers through standard service interfaces, combining elements of management service components as type A, B and C [19], as illustrated in Figure 14 and adding features as management capability exposure, as an association between the management service components information and instance management services. 3GPP [19] defines the service-based management architecture as the Management Function-(MF), the entities which are playing the role of Management Service (MS) producer and MS consumer, including interactions between them through requests and responses communication paradigm.

Data analytics capabilities in the 5G network offers to the management system information to improve the 5G services or 5G network performance or future prediction through the collected data from the network (services, slices, network function, infrastructure), defined as in [19].

Figure 14: 5G management service component types

2.3.1 ETSI NFV MANO

5G Management & Orchestration chains the Virtualized Network Functions (VNFs) with other VNFs and/or Physical Network Functions (PNFs) to realize a Network Service (NS) that will be further mapped into Network Slices. NFV architectural framework identifies functional blocks and the main reference points between such blocks. Some of these are already present in current deployments (EM and OSS/BSS), whilst others (NFV-MANO) [20] will be needed in order to support the virtualization process and consequent operation. NFV-MANO functions (NFVO, VNFM and VIM) [20] play an important role in delivering the business benefits envisioned by the NFV technology. To do so, interworking with other functional components in the NFV framework, as well as external entities, such as Operations and Business Support Systems (OSS/BSS) is required.

2.3.2 Cloud Native orchestration

It has been demonstrated that on the bare-metal server an improved efficiency can be achieved, by splitting the resources in smaller pieces of servers. Also, the 5G Core Service-Based-Architecture is a cloud native implementation. It may be concluded that containers represent the virtualization technology evolution, running the underlying microservices on top of the OS. Container's microservices architecture benefits can be identified as efficient resource consumption, faster service creation, deployment and reduced apps booting time, lower costs, scalability, resiliency, portability, OS independence. K8s [21] is one of the container's orchestration tools, the open-source system for automating the containerized application deployment, scaling and management.

2.3.3 Transport network orchestration

The 5G transport network is providing connectivity between different network elements, from gNBs, Packet Core and Data Network. To address the required 5G network configuration and end-to-end service slice deployment the transport network should be programmable, elastic and flexible, ready for dynamically changing of configuration, traffic flows and QoS service assurance implementation for applications requiring eMBB, URLLC or mMTC. The transport network orchestration, addressing different types of transport network implementation (wired, optical WDM, wireless MWs, ethernet, IP/MPLS, Segment Routing, Data Centre networking).

2.3.4 Resources, slices and services orchestration

The orchestration layer takes care of initial deployment of the services involving different network domains, such as RAN, Core or Transport Network (TN) in a coordinated resources allocation method, VNFs or CNF deployment and service chaining. The orchestration is enabling the service deployment across the facilities, dynamic resource allocation, service composing and onboarding, slice creation. The facility resources orchestration can be both 3GPP MANO compliant for VNFs in VMs implementations or Cloud native compliant for microservices architectures.

2.3.5 Development and deployment tools and software

5G services deployment in the concept of SBA requires the adoption of tools to transform the facility implementation, from dedicated bare-metal network functions to Software network functions through virtualization concepts, enabling the automation of the services deployment and configuration, network resource management and slices creation. These software components and tools may be retrieved in the VITAL-5G facilities.

- **CI/CD** or Continuous Integration and Continuous Delivery is the framework for creating a build and running automated software application tests and to extend the integrations to deploy all code changes to a testing and production environment. CI/CD tools for automated and continuous testing solutions to create the pipelines are **Jenkins** [22], **Bamboo** [23], **GitLab** [24], **Drone.io** [25].
- **Openstack** [26] is the cloud operating system that controls large pools of compute, storage, and networking resources throughout a datacenter, providing standard IaaS functionality, orchestration, service management and user applications deployment, Cloud Infrastructure for Virtual Machines, and Containers.
- **Docker** [27] is the open platform for developing, shipping, and running applications, by separating the applications from the infrastructure so the software can be quickly delivered. An application is running in a loosely isolated environment called a container, for a fast-consistent app deployment.
- **Kubernetes** [21] is an open-source system for automating deployment, scaling and management of containerized applications. Kubernetes is the cloud native applications orchestrator.
- **OSM** [28] is the open source ETSI NFV Management and Orchestration (MANO) stack for E2E network service orchestration for telco services. OSM key aspects are the Information Model aligned with ETSI NFV SOL006, the unified Northbound interfaces (NBIs) based in SOL005, Network Services extension across multiple-domain and Life Cycle Management of Network Slices.
- **ONAP** [29] is a comprehensive platform for orchestration, management, and automation of network and edge computing services for network operators, cloud providers, and enterprises. It also provides real-time, policy-driven orchestration, services automation and Life Cycle management for 5G next-generation services and networks.
- **Prometheus** [30] is an open-source monitoring and alerting system that collects metrics as series data. The data is stored on a single server node, the data collection is pulled/pushed and multiple modes of graph are supported. The tool works well for machine centric monitoring or monitoring of highly dynamic service-oriented architectures.
- **Grafana** [31] is the open-source multi-platform analytics and interactive visualization web application, allowing dynamic dashboards creation for centralized data analysis, visualization and alerting.

2.4 Network and services monitoring in 5G deployments

Another key component in 5G networks is represented by network and services monitoring capabilities, the process of data collection of a variety of metrics, benefitting by different open software tools used for monitoring (e.g., Prometheus) and data presenting through dashboards. The monitoring stream is focused on two main streams:

- Infrastructure monitoring, collecting the data from the infrastructure components, e.g., UE, RAN, Core network, Transport, virtualized infrastructure, MEC;
- Network and service performance monitoring, evaluating network resources, services status, users.

5G networks have to perform the monitoring process, for resources and elasticity profiling, testing and services validation, gathering general information about network infrastructure but also about the 5G services and related slices parameters. In 5G, the service is monitored since the deployment phase, the services specific metrics and KPIs are collected and further used for preventive activities, network control, quality measurements, fault detections and E2E validation. The 5G monitoring framework is highlighted in Figure 15.

Figure 15: 5G SA monitoring framework

The key requirement in 5G networks is related to the Performance Monitoring (PM), represented by the active measurements of the E2E QoS and QoE KPIs. The PM includes, on the one hand, the traditional indicators, such as throughput and latency, but on the other hand, the SLA assurance, QoS monitoring, real time resources monitoring and data acquisition layer for dashboard data visualization.

2.5 5G slicing concepts in 3GPP Rel.16

As defined by [70] the general concept of Network Slicing is characterized by a logical network that provides specific network capabilities and characteristics, being composed of different 5G network domain components, as RAN, Core and transport, as defined in [15], provides a clear definition of several key concepts, as the network slice or the network slice instance as a set of service level requirements associated with various Service Level Agreements, are requested to be satisfied by the communication service providers.

By communicating using the network slicing, the 5G system architecture [15] defines two main concepts and background: (1) **the end-to-end slice concepts and characteristics** and (2) **the management of the 5G network slices**. Those aspects are considering the 5G Network view and the 5G Management view, as in Figure 4, several examples of how network slices can be delivered for communication services.

Figure 16: Management 5G network slice subnet instance

The network slices are managed in a manner of subsequent phases, from the Preparation to the proper Life Cycle of the Instances and ending to the decommissioning phase. There are several key features of 5G in Rel.16, focusing on enhancements to URLLC, Network Slicing, Edge Computing, Non-Public Networks. The Rel.16 is addressing several limitations in terms of the network slicing, as the 5GC interworking enhancement for the PDU data session and providing advanced support of Network Slice Specific Authentication and Authorization. Also, the 3GPP Rel.16 technical report [7] provides an enhancement for management and orchestration for the 5G Network and Slicing, including the performance measurement in tenant's environment and network slice supervision. New business roles and models are possible in the 5G systems, services exposure and control to the 3rd parties, SLA impact on network slice management, addressing also security relationship between several entities, as: (1) UEs and specific private slices, (2) The envisioned private slices and networks, (3) Private slice and others slices of the same networks. Lastly, it provides several enhancements of performance assurances for 5G networks, including network slicing.

3 VITAL-5G testbeds initial setup

This chapter is detailing the existing capabilities of the VITAL-5G testbeds, as they have been collected starting with **Month 6** of the project (T3.1 start) by evaluating the 5G technology availability for RAN, Core and transport network. The evaluation of the initial setup is correlated also with the 5G required features described in Chapter 2, identifying from this stage all the necessary upgrades and integrations needed for 5G SA target testbeds.

A summary of the **testbed's capabilities** is presented in Table 3, providing the testbed's early expected resources availability at project start. Even the existing technologies presented are not fully available from begin, following the VITAL-5G reference architecture, described in Chapter 4, all the hardware and software components are integrated in the 5G SA Rel.16., through several integration phases, as presented in Chapter 6, for testbeds and trials site facility.

Table 3: VITAL-5G actual testbeds description

5G Infra\ Testbed	RAN NSA/SA	5GCN NSA/SA	IP Transport	IaaS	MANO	Security	MEC	Slicing
Athens	Ericsson	Athonet Griffone	Cisco Huawei	Openstack	OSMv110	IPsec	No MEC installed. Justification provided in 3.3.2	UPF instances
Antwerp	Ericsson	Nokia CMU	Nokia DWDM	Openstack	OSMS	IPsec	Collocated with core	IP based slicing
Bucharest Galati	Huawei SRAN17 SA/NSA Mosaic5g	Ericsson 2.15 Nokia CMU21.1 Mosaic5G	Cisco NXOS IPFABRIC	Openstack Ussuri Kubernetes	OSMv10 10.0.2	Fortigate 1000D DDOS	Collocated IaaS with 5G Core	APN based

3.1 Galati (Danube) 5G-Testbed architecture

The Romanian VITAL-5G testbed is designed and build as an adaptive 5G architecture evolving to 3GPP Release 16. The testbed is composed by the 5G network elements and infrastructure existing from other projects, mainly based on ICT-17 5G-EVE [8]. When describing the existing testbed architecture, we are presenting the existing capabilities, already deployed in Orange network within the project scope, focusing on the following:

- 5G RAN and Core components, software and hardware (NSA)
- 5G transport network
- Virtualized environment, Openstack based and Kubernetes
- Orchestration, OSM related.

Figure 17: VITAL-5G Orange testbed infrastructure

As seen in Figure 17, the testbed network elements for RAN, Core, Virtualization and Network are deployed in two phases, 5G NSA and 5G SA.

Phase 1:

Testbed deployment started with a 5G NSA implementation in Bucharest, for early trials, with the 5G NSA RAN and Core Option 3x. There has also been introduced an advanced IP/Network infrastructure, IP-FABRIC [33] architecture network for cloud services delivery and an IP network open for transport service orchestration. Within the scope of VITAL-5G, it has been implemented an advanced telco cloud infrastructure for VNF, CNF and bare metal services apps, supporting IaaS/CaaS over Openstack and Kubernetes/Docker.

Phase 2:

In the 2nd phase, Orange's testbed is expected to implement a 5G service over standalone network in a private mobile network concept, that is integrated in the Bucharest testbed and is 3GPP Release 16. The 5G is running on dedicated virtualized infrastructure, 5G SA option 2 implementations as seen in Figure 2.

Figure 18: 5G SA implementation in the Romanian testbed

3.1.1 RAN architecture

From all available 5G NSA architecture options, Orange Romania started its 5G deployment in n78 band (3.5 GHz) using 5G NSA Option 3x. By using 4G as the anchor point of the control plane, a good service continuity can be met while supporting rapid network construction in the initial stage of 5G deployment.

Considering n78 is a TDD band and that the DL traffic is considerably higher than the UL, and also due to coexistence of LTE TDD in 3.5 GHz spectrum, ORO selected 8:2 the DL/UL timeslot ratio (DDDDDDSUU with a 3ms shift, with 5 ms repetition, as illustrated in Figure 19). In the Bucharest Orange Romania 5G Lab the DL/UL slot assignment has been configured 4:1 (DDDSU with 2.5 ms repetition), as there is no LTE TDD deployment. If the traffic pattern on certain sites indicates that the UL traffic has a higher percentage than the DL, then the DL/UL timeslot ratio may be changed to ensure best 5G performance [35].

Figure 19: NR radio frame structure and with ORO DL/UL configuration in LTE TDD ecosystem

As described for [Phase 1](#) step, in Galati the 5G site specifically designed for VITAL-5G project was installed and integrated by Orange in H1 2021 in NSA configuration and consists of two 5G sectors (two n78 cells for NR and 2 LTE 800 cells as the anchor for 5G in NSA configuration) that covers NAVROM ships positions

and headquarter, as presented in the coverage simulation output from Figure 20. The red coverage is for NR sector 1 and the blue one corresponds to NR sector 2.

Figure 20: 5G Galati site coverage simulation map with the use case interest area representation

Table 4: ORO Testbed – Lab 5G cells

SITE NAME	gNB ID	NR CELL NAME	NRDUCELL ID	PCI	C I	TX and RX Mode	BAN D	BW
gNodeB_10_UPB	300103	gNBLAB10_UPB_indoor_NR37_1	1	110	1	4 TX and 4 RX	N78	100 MHz
gNodeB_10_UPB	300103	gNBLAB10_UPB_box_NR37_2	2	210	2	4 TX and 4 RX	N78	100 MHz

Table 5: ORO Testbed – Galati 5G cells

SITE NAME	gNB ID	NR CELL NAME	NR DUCELLID	PCI	CI	TX and RX Mode	BAND	BW
GA0039_NR	700397	GA0039_NR_1	1	0	1	64 TX and 64 RX	N78	100 MHz
GA0039_NR	700397	GA0039_NR_2	2	1	2	64 TX and 64 RX	N78	100 MHz

3.1.2 Distributed cloud\MEC

The MEC design of the testbed is following the recommendation from Chapter 2 and the deployment is possible to be done in Bucharest testbed using the computing infrastructure.

Figure 21: MEC analysis in Galati

The extension facility in Galati is connected via the IP multi-protocol label switching (IP/MPLS) high speed technology with 10Gbps links to our central cluster which performs advanced network control functions, as well as analytics, computation and data storage. The proposed design is taking into consideration all the network segments and transmission characteristics, for latency between UE and base station (URLCC slice) $\approx 3\text{ms}$, gNB to 5GCN $\approx 1.5\text{ms}$ and 5GCN to MEC less than 1ms , as they are collocated and fiber links interconnected, offering the E2E delay budget of $\approx 4.5\text{ms}$, under analysis from the Network Application perspective.

3.1.3 Core architecture

Orange 5G core testbed is based on virtualized network infrastructure, for both 5G core options, the NSA and SA and is aligned with the Core characteristics defined in Chapter 2.

The NSA Core architecture, is composed of a vEPC deployed in an Openstack infrastructure. The existing core architecture can support broadband connectivity, configurable UL/DL speed at UE level at increased rate, $\approx 1000\text{Mbps}$ for DL and $\approx 100\text{Mbps}$ for UL. For the existing core architecture, the 5G services are manually configured, by using dedicated APNs and network provisioned capabilities in terms of throughput, as the main use case that can be served by this architecture is mainly the eMBB.

3.1.4 Network and management functions

In the testbed OSMv10 is Orange's orchestrator that is compliant with ETSI MANO architecture and is offering an orchestrator tool that integrates with infrastructure controllers and can build different VNFs and Network Slices across all the platforms inside the lab. It can connect and communicate with VIM for virtualized segment and from the container segment. It will act as an umbrella deployment and management tool for different slice networking deployment, 5G ready use cases.

Ansible [39] and Terraform [40] are the automation core tools triggered from CI/CD managers that creates the automation back bone of the 5G lab used for provisioning and configurations of any applications. This tool is closing the loop of automation in VITAL-5G and makes the environment ready for any integration oriented in 5G SA present and future use cases.

3.1.5 Virtualized Network infrastructure

Inside this testbed, Orange envisioned a datacenter composed of several racks' units full of network and compute equipment's from various technology brands like Cisco, Fortinet, HP, Nokia and Huawei ready to host and accommodate applications and services for a 5G ready network and services, using the following virtualization environment software tools, aligned to Chapter 2:

1. Openstack Ussuri distributed cluster based on containers.
2. ESXi VMWare [41] cluster
3. Container Kubernetes cluster

Vmware ESXi [41] cluster is installed on 2 nodes (VITAL-5G-node10 and VITAL-5G-node11) with shared storage on VITAL-5G-storage01 for shared OS images and vSphere client hosting. In the picture below, it is shown an overall information view about the cluster from vSphere web interface. This virtualization solution is dedicated to host the development VMs of the VITAL-5G platform, both production and pre-production. Rancher is a containers orchestrator based on Kubernetes that is making easy for development, operations, testing and management of containers.

3.1.6 Transport

Orange testbed is an IP/MPLS transport network, consisting of the access, aggregation and core network layers, interconnected through high-speed links, 100 Gbps broadband connectivity between the network elements, Qos control and fast services delivery. The 5G testbed focus is mainly for the integration and deployment of the architecture in the Data Centre (DCs), designed as a core network element for the IaaS/CaaS integration for the Network Application deployment and also for the 5GCN components within the virtualized environment.

The 5G testbed is split into three main components:

- 5G transport network in the Bucharest testbed, deployed as a cluster of advanced network equipment, in the DC, mainly for the integration of the virtualized infrastructure and 5GCN.
- 5G transport network in Galati, deployed as an extension of the IP network infrastructure for the gNB aggregation and Network Application experimentation on Galati.
- E2E transport network service configuration, manual configuration of the network, dedicated traffic VPNs, QoS definition and service traffic and KPIs assurance.

Within the scope of VITAL-5G the transport network has been designed in order to fulfill the 5G transport requirements, through the architecture illustrated in Figure 23, with 2 main key characteristics: (1) to ensure the high transport capacity and QoS for the further network service slices transported by the network; (2) to provide dynamically resiliency and redundant transport paths; (3) to offer the automatically E2E transport network configuration and orchestration, not available in this phase.

Figure 22: VITAL-5G Romanian testbed transport design

The DC transport solution is using the IPFABRIC [33] concept, using BGP EVPN as control plane and VXLAN as data plane encapsulation. The solution offers a lot of benefits versus the legacy layer-oriented Datacenters using Core, Distribution and Access layers respectively.

3.1.7 Testbed monitoring

The Orange testbed monitoring solution is based on the framework presented in Chapter 2 and defined in Figure 2 , as the collection of the data from the acquisition layer of the different infrastructure sources, key collection components as 5G NSA/SA Core and RAN and Transport network is being prepared. The collection of the data related to the Configuration Management (CM) and Fault Management (FM) is also being envisioned.

3.2 Antwerp 5G-Testbed

The Antwerp VITAL-5G testbed is built based on commercial network infrastructure in Port of Antwerp area. Existing commercial towers are reused as much as possible to deploy VITAL 5G testbed equipment together with dedicated new builds for coverage enhancement. The user traffic and network management of the commercial network and testbed are isolated either physically or logically. The reused and shared infrastructure includes:

- Up to 8x cellular towers, radio equipment cabinets, power supply, etc.

Shared but logically isolated infrastructure is:

- 5G SA UEs and SIM cards.

Please note that due to change of network supplier on legacy network, during Phase 2 upgrade the 2/3/4G network infrastructure is also swapped. This means in Phase 2 the 5G NSA network environment is also different from Phase 1. To relate to the 5G network evolution in Section 2.2, the complete evolution process will go through Option 3x (Figure 7) to reach Option 2.

The deployment of 5G infrastructure will start with Option 3x and end with Option 2 (plus legacy Option 1). The reasons to select Option 3x as 5G NSA deployment strategy are:

- Support fast 5G deployment and good mobility support,
- Minimum user plan data exchange on X2 interface, high peak performance and throughput,
- The service continuity with limited 5G coverage by the LTE layer and EN-DC support UE ecosystem,
- Support smooth evolution to SA option 2.

The advantages of evolving from Option 3x to SA Option 2 are:

- Direct link between 5G gNB and 5GC has no impact on existing 4G network,
- Fast support of 5G SA and network slicing,
- Smooth 4G & 5G user separation and migration.

3.2.1 RAN architecture

Current available spectrum resource of Telenet and the deployment scenario is described in Table 7 below:

Table 6: Current available spectrum resource of Telenet

Band	Frequency	Technology	Bandwidth	Scenario
N1	1935-1950 / 2125-2140	FDD NR	2x 15MHz	Macro
N78	3600-3650	TDD NR	50MHz	Macro / small cell
B20	791-801 / 832-842	FDD LTE	2x 10MHz	Macro
B3	1760-1780 / 1855-1875	FDD LTE	2x 20MHz	Macro /small cell anchor
B7	2535-2550 / 2655-2670	FDD LTE	2x 15MHz	Macro

700MHz spectrum is currently not available. It is estimated to be available in H2 2022. Combining spectrum resource and RAN evolution strategy, the result is:

- In NSA Option 3x setup, LTE B3 will be used as anchoring band, NR N1 and/or NR N78 will be added for user plane traffic. B3 and B7 will also be available for CA on LTE.
- In SA Option 2 setup, 5G UE will attach to N1, N78 or N1 + N78 in CA mode for network slicing.

In SA Option 2 mode, the network is expected to support several types of network slices, including:

- eMBB: a network slice has a high requirement on guaranteed bandwidth.
- mMTC/URLLC: a network slice with low or ultra-low latency and high or ultra-high reliability requirement for critical data.
- mMTC/MIoT: a network slice for machine communication carries non-essential data.

Note that the IoT slices use separated spectrum from eMBB/URLLC slices. Thus, full RAN slicing is not required on spectrums of IoT slices. The slicing functionality is only defined on the core network.

The coverage of the 5G network is greatly affected by NR spectrum, NR mode, transmit power and actual propagation path in the coverage area. As higher spectrum has higher propagation loss compared to lower spectrum, thus using lower bands can improve 5G coverage and field strength. As mentioned in table above, the limiting factor of network coverage will be 5G NR on 3.5GHz. As NR on 3500MHz is in TDD mode, the frame structure with different DL/UL time slot allocation can impact the DL/UL bandwidth. The transmit power allowed by regulation in different regions also impact the 5G MCL. Telenet decided to use DDDSU TDD pattern with 2.5ms repetition period and 10:2:2 for downlink, gap and uplink symbols in the special slot. Resource allocation in one sub-frame is concluded as following in Figure 24.

The frame structure is illustrated in Figure 24.

Figure 24: 5G TDD frame structure for Antwerp testbed

Summarizing both factors mentioned above, together with current granted radiation license and geographical data of pilot area, the simulation of 5G coverage in pilot are presented in Figure 23.

Figure 25: Estimated Telenet 3.5 GHz coverage in Port of Antwerp

3.2.2 Distributed cloud\MEC

The available MEC setup in Phase 1 is designed for graphic computing and rendering for VR services, which is not sufficient or applicable for VITAL-5G. Thus, a complete redesign is needed for the Network Applications requirements.

Figure 26: Legacy MEC setup for graphic rendering

The rendering rack consist of 6x NVIDIA 2080 GPUs and management functions, which is connected to location 5G network directly via fiber patching. The distance between 5G radio and 5G core is 150 km and local edge is optimized to reduce latency and improve reliability. As for VITAL 5G the MEC infrastructure required for Network Application are very different, 5G service area is large and transport network is much more complicated, if MEC is designed differently as described in Section 6.4.

3.2.3 Core architecture

The Phase 1 5G core testbed is based on virtualized network infrastructure. As mentioned, this vEPC setup will be swapped by new vendor solution which supports 2/3/4/5G unified core including 5G SA. As solution is already swapped, the capabilities and features are not described in detail. Please refer to Section 6.2 for details of Phase 2 upgrade.

Figure 27: 5G vEPC of Phase 1 Antwerp testbed

3.2.4 Network and management functions

The network management system in Phase 1 is built on VMWare environment. Same as mentioned before the system is swap in Phase 2 thus details are not described.

Figure 28: Legacy network management system of Antwerp testbed

3.2.5 Network infrastructure

In Phase 1 the network infrastructure is a hybrid design with both private virtualized environment and public cloud. The private virtualized environment is based on Openstack on 2x HP servers. The resource on this environment is limited and mostly functions as a protocol gateway. The cloud environment is based on Azure and the resource on-demand. The connection between private and cloud environment is by Telenet gateway to provide security and optimized latency. This setup is not designed for VITAL-5G and will be upgraded in Phase 2. Please refer to Section 6.4.3 for more details.

3.2.6 Transport

The transport network of the existing testbed is built towards vEPC, which is located in a lab environment instead of one of Telenet’s datacenters. As mentioned before this network design is phased out in phase 2. Thus, details of the transport network are not described in detail. Please refer to Section 6 for description of transport network of VITAL-5G testbed.

Figure 29: Transport network of existing Telenet 5G testbed

3.2.7 Testbed monitoring

The existing network monitoring provides KPIs of 5G NSA network based on 4G tools, without any monitoring on 5G SA traffic or NS related KPIs. For RAN, core and transmission network the monitoring is available in Table 7.

Table 7: Telenet testbed monitoring

Radio side	Core side	Transport
Alarms	Alarms	Alarms
RRC Setup Success Rate	EPS attach/dedicated bearer attach success rate	Load monitoring
Paging Discard Rate	Service request success rate	Latency probing
Handover success rate (inter-RAT & intra-RAT)	User service setup time	IP traffic usage
Number of RRC connected	network performance monitor in real-time	
PRB allocation per user		
Average throughput per user (DL & UL)		
Peak throughput (DL & UL)		

3.3 Athens 5G-testbed

Athens testbed will be used in UC#3 validation and it is based on 5G SA architecture. More specifically, the trials will take place in Diakinisis warehouse where the RAN will be installed. The Packet Core will be installed in OTE’s premises and the interconnection between the two sites will be achieved through the public transport network. In this section the network architecture is described, providing detailed information about its components.

3.3.1 RAN architecture

For the needs of Automation and remote of freight logistics use case, a radio access network will be installed in Diakinisis premises targets to cover an area of 1200m² (Figure 30). The radio will be based on

New Radio (NR) technology, and it will be connected to a 5GC that is located in OTE premises. NR is planned to be integrated from the beginning with the SA Rel. 16 architecture, 5G RAN characteristics being described in Table 8, as based on this deployment it is provided the coverage area for picking rooms, cooling or checking rooms as seen in Figure 30.

Table 8: Athens testbed RAN equipment

Type	Manufacturer	Model	Description	Qty
Radio Unit	Ericsson	ERS4408	LTE/NR TDD with four duplex TX/RX branches supporting up to 4x5 W output power	2
Network Equipment	Ericsson	6630	Baseband Unit, 15 CPRI/9 eCPRI, LTE+NR with up to 12 CCs LTE and 12 CCs NR in dual mixed mode	1
Transport		IDU	FO Bridge	1

Figure 30: 5G covered area at DIAKINISIS premises

3.3.2 Distributed cloud\MEC

The Greek testbed will be implemented for the needs of VITAL-5G project during the second phase of the network architecture and implementation procedure. Its architecture will be based on the 5G-EVE Greek testbed, which is implemented and tested successfully.

The two main sites of the implementation are the Core site, where the packet core is installed, and the RAN site, where the access part of the network is installed. The distance between the two sites is about 25km. In between there is the packet optical transport network (POTP), which includes the transport network and several network elements, such as servers and switches. OTE L2/L3 OSN switches are

interconnected to the OTE IP Core, using a 10 Gbps capacity line, to interconnect 5G-EVE Greek site infrastructure located at OTE Labs in Psalidi-Attica (Core site) with the RAN site. Additionally, KPIs measuring probes have been installed for measuring network performance and service layer metrics in real time to validate KPIs of the network.

The transport network delay is measured to be 200ns. However, the rest of the network elements are adding extra latency. The values were collected during the period of 7/7/2021 to 9/7/2021 and the average measured value for latency was 1.23ms, while the minimum was 1ms and the maximum was 1.3ms.

In the Greek testbed, the transport latency that will be avoided is only 200ns according the measured latency results, that type of implementation will not offer any significant advantage, therefore, a MEC implementation in Core could be an alternative architecture.

3.3.3 Core architecture

Currently a 5G NSA packet core is installed in OTE's premises. However, for the needs of VITAL-5G, it is planned to be upgraded in 5G SA Rel. 16 based on the architecture presented in Figure 31, using ATHONET Griffone R2.0, which is an enhanced implementation of network functions.

Figure 31: Athonet Griffone Architecture

CPF includes the four main functions that are used in the SA architecture, the AMF, the SMF, the AUSF and the UDM. In Figure 32 the CPF internal architecture is presented as well as the interconnection between the Functions.

Figure 32: Control Plane Function architecture

Multiple RANs could be connected to Griffon and access AMF. For UC#3 where the testbed will be used, one RAN will be installed, which will include two Radio Units. Additionally, Griffone exposes the following standardized interfaces that are described by 3GPP.

3.3.4 Network and management functions

The Open-Source MANO (OSM) will be used for the orchestration of the GR testbed. The design-time scope of OSM includes: i) the capability for Create/Read/Update/Delete (CRUD) operations on the Network Service definition, ii) tools for VNF Package Generation, iii) Graphical User Interface (GUI) to accelerate the design time phase, VNFs on-boarding and deployment. On the other hand, the run-time scope of OSM mostly provides: i) an automated Service Orchestration environment as the main coordination engine, ii) plugins for integrating multiple Virtual Infrastructure Managers - VIMs (including

OpenStack, VMWare, Amazon Web Services, OpenVIM) and Kubernetes Clusters iii) plugins for integrating multiple SDN controllers, iv) an integrated generic VNFM with support for integrating specific VNFs from VNF vendors, v) support to integrate Physical Network Functions into Network Services.

The OSM Release 10 will be used for the VITAL-5G project, which includes relevant features in the direction of the increased compliance with the ETSI NFV standards:

- SOL006 [71] alignment, including a translator CLI tool to adopt descriptors from previous SOL versions,
- Scaling for Kubernetes Applications, which improves scalability in Kubernetes deployments,
- Improved Scale-in/Scale-out functionality, allowing operators to trigger scaling operations from the Graphical User Interface in addition to the Command Line,
- Reduced footprint and improved release process, relying on Python packages with locked dependency versions and greatly reduced image sizes,
- Software-Defined Network Platforms support, managed by a WAN Infrastructure Manager (WIM).

The setup of the GR testbed OSM and its interconnection with the VITAL-5G main platform are depicted in Figure 33.

Figure 33: Interconnection of GR testbed OSM with VITAL-5G platform

3.3.5 Network infrastructure

The detailed network design is presented in Figure 34. Currently, 5GC installation is in progress in OTE's premises, where Athonet Griffone will be used. Additionally, the OSM deployment is starting. For its installation a server with the following characteristics will be used: Model: DL360 Gen9, CPU: 2x E5-2650, RAM: 4 x 32=128GB, 4 x 600GB Disks.

Figure 34: Athens testbed design

At Diakinisis premises, where the RAN will be installed, the study about the RAN design and the required equipment is completed.) The radio units and the BBU exact locations are presented in the top view of the Diakinisis warehouse in Figure 35.

Figure 35: Diakinisis warehouse top view with radio units and BBU location

3.3.6 Transport

RAN and Packet Core interconnection will be achieved through the public transport network. The distance between Diakinisis warehouse and OTE premises is about 25 km and the fiber optics link extension is under construction. The transport network will include:

- High Speed 10Gbps Connection
- IP/MPLS Core infrastructure
- Local Access Network Segments
 - Huawei Packet Over Transport Equipment; Cisco 10/100Gbps LAN Switches

Figure 36: Athens testbed end-to-end design

3.3.7 Testbed monitoring

In order to monitor testbed KPIs and ensure the network QoS, several monitoring tools (probes and a management server) are planned to be installed. These tools are not part of the testbed, but external pieces of equipment that will be installed in several spots within the network, such as in the RAN and in the packet core, as it is presented in Figure 37. The monitoring tools could allow the accurate measurement of both the network parameters monitoring and the time relevant parameters (such as packet loss or latency). More specifically, these tools will provide values about:

- Latency (packets will be transferred through the network), Throughput (UL and DL throughput)
- Availability and reliability (by measuring the packet error rate at the IP/Application layer)

Figure 37: GR testbed network topology with measuring tools included

4 VITAL-5G E2E Facility reference architecture

The **reference architecture** is the VITAL-5G approach/ blueprint for designing and building the 5G system, providing a comprehensive overview of the technology and solution provided. It is based on two of the main pillars, the **facility overall concept**, providing the envisioned architecture that should answer to the VITAL-5G and the **Network Application** concepts. The targeted reference architecture is providing open 5G distributed testbeds (*Objective 3*), virtualized and flexible and associated vertical's infrastructure to enable T&L Network Application testing, validation and experimentation in real condition.

The VITAL-5G **E2E facility architecture**, represents the innovative technical solution and implementation framework for the 5G communication services required by the T&L industry's verticals. The architecture definition is trying also to cover today's existing mismatches between Telco infrastructures and verticals, namely: (1) where network services can be deployed, (2) capabilities of dynamic services setup over 5G infrastructures with respect to testbeds available resources and interfaces interconnections and (3) new Vertical's Network Application interactions and trials in real T&L flexible infrastructures. The E2E architectures applies to all the three testbeds, meaning that the 5G technologies, capabilities and features presented are available in **Athens, Antwerp** and **Galati** testbeds.

4.1 VITAL-5G Architecture definition and network components

The VITAL-5G architecture is oriented to offer a flexible platform adapted to serve the specific needs of the T&L sector focused on the creation, deployment, management and validation of Network Application and it provides a functional architecture for the Network Application 5G connectivity. In VITAL-5G the architecture is defined with the support of the relevant 5G testbed's related network component, in order to fulfill the requirements of the Network Application deployment over 5G infrastructure. As expected, the base of the proposed architecture is composed by: (1) **Virtualized Infrastructure environment**, (2) **Network Functions** communication framework – through REST APIs, (3) **5G RAN** and (4) the Core functions, as the target architecture for VITAL-5G testbeds is 3GPP Rel. 16 compliant.

The scope of the architecture is not only to present the network and software components used in VITAL-5G, but to design the 5G E2E architectural reference and deployment approach to fulfill from the technical perspective the Network Application needs and to cover the existing technology gaps. The definition of the architecture is based on a collection of 5G components, resources and features, as seen in Table 9, aligned with Section 2 requirements in terms of 5G SA networks, state-of-the-art of the testbeds and expected evolution as described in Section 3 and then evaluated as 5G Testbed and Infrastructure upgrades and integration, as presented in Chapter 6.

Table 9: 5G system and network resources

5G NF	RAN	Core	Transport	MEC
Features	NSA/SA	NSA/SA	Layer Architecture	Apps Platform
3GPP Rel15/Rel16	eNB/gNB Physical/VMs	vEPC/5GCN Virtualized	QoS/QoE Service Flow	System management
Slicing	APN NSSAI/SST	APN NSSAI/SST	QoS DSCP MPLS	E2E slicing
Security	Security Architecture and Procedures ENISA Security reports			
Orchestration	OSS/BSS	OSS/BSS OSM	Network Orchestrator	OSM

The architecture is aiming to support the E2E network slice services, through orchestration and automation and enhanced slice management and monitoring. By defining the NBIs for testbeds to platform integration, it facilitates the verticals’ and 3rd party integration in the ecosystem and the end-to-end vertical’s use cases validation and experimentation, as support for trials.

4.2 Facility Interfaces and APIs

It is relevant to mention at this stage the definition of the Platform-to-testbeds interfaces, for all the three testbeds. The interface between the VITAL-5G platform and the VITAL-5G testbeds has been introduced in D1.2 [42], identifying the main functionalities to be exposed by each testbed towards the common platform. As mentioned in [42] and shown in Figure 38 (reported here for completeness) the VITAL-5G platform interacts with the various testbeds through a unified South-Bound Interface (SBI) implemented through common APIs, while the translation between the specific interfaces implemented by the testbed management, monitoring and orchestration platforms and these common APIs is handled through testbed-specific plugins to be implemented in WP3. Such plugins, when required, will implement the translation between the messages, protocols and information models adopted in the particular testbed and the common messages expected at the unified SBI of the VITAL-5G platform. This approach will enable the seamless interoperability of the various testbeds with the centralized platform.

The features and capabilities offered by individual testbeds may be slightly different. For example, the programmable APIs to dynamically create new custom network slices is not available in all testbeds, at least initially, and some of them will pre-configure manually a set of slices to be used for the experimental actions. The set of functionalities supported by each testbed will be captured in the information stored at the VITAL-5G Platform Inventory, so that the platform components will be able to adapt their behavior and procedures accordingly. With reference to the previous example, when provisioning a new vertical service, the VITAL-5G platform will decide whether to ask for a new slice or select an existing one depending on the capabilities offered by the target testbed.

Figure 38: Interfacing between VITAL-5G Platform and VITAL-5G testbeds

In Table 10 the main functionalities to be offered by the various testbeds and the corresponding abstract interfaces are specified. In summary the following functions should be supported:

- Network slice management, for creation, selection and configuration of network slices in the 5G infrastructure deployed in a VITAL-5G testbed (Slice_conf interface);

- Onboarding of Network Application and VNF packages and network service descriptors for vertical services in the orchestration platform at the edge/cloud computing infrastructure of a VITAL-5G testbed (Nfvo_cat interface);
- Provisioning and lifecycle management of network services for the instantiation of vertical services composed by Network Application (Nfvo_lcm interface);
- Configuration (Mon_conf) and retrieval through a publish/subscribe mechanism (Mon_pub) of monitoring data, for both service and infrastructure KPIs, including 5G network KPIs and metrics related to the consumption of computing resources.

In the following Table 10 the reference APIs selected for the implementation of the abstract interfaces are reported:

Table 10: VITAL-5G Platform South-bound Interface

Testbed system	Interface	Reference standards	Implementation
NFV MANO System	Nfvo_cat: management of VNF packages and Network Service Descriptors.	ETSI NFV SOL 006 [43] for NFV descriptors ETSI NFV SOL 005 [44] for REST API on management of VNF packages and NSDs	OSM 10 NBI API [48], for: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • VNFD Details • NSD Details • PDU Details
	Nfvo_lcm: Management of the lifecycle of NFV Network Services and configuration of their virtual functions	ETSI NFV SOL 005 [44] for REST API on lifecycle management of NFV network services Non-standard extensions for configuration of VNFs, adopting the ETSI OSM mechanisms for VNF configuration.	OSM 10 NBI API [49] , for: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • NSLCM Details OSM based Day-1 and Day-2 operations for VNF configuration [49]
5G Slice Management System	Slice_conf	3GPP TS 28.531 [45] for REST API to create Network Slice Instances 3GPP TS 28.541 [46] for the information model on network slices	Implementation in progress.
Monitoring System	Mon_conf Mon_pub	-- --	REST APIs for monitoring configuration (implementation in progress). Publish/subscribe mechanism for publication of monitoring data, based on Kafka bus, adopting 5G

			EVE information models. For further details, refer to 5G EVE D3.4 [47] section 3.4.3.1 (topics for publishing data) and 3.4.3.3 (information model of the messages).
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4.3 VITAL-5G Platform integration with the testbeds

The VITAL-5G platform, hosted on the **Orange Romania** testbed, as a centralized service, securely deployed, is requiring communications flows, with the VITAL-5G testbeds and developers. They are provided secure VPN connectivity solution, as detailed later, seen in Figure 39.

Figure 39: 5G testbeds connectivity to the platform components

The integration of the testbeds to the Platform is a mandatory integration step for further Network Application onboarding and experimentation activities and it is implemented within the E2E reference architecture scope. Further details regarding the connectivity are defined in Chapter 5.

5 VITAL-5G Security implementations

One of the project objectives is to deliver **security** regarding the VITAL-5G Platform and testbeds, as security is a general VITAL-5G concern, extending and implementing the security overview described in Section 2. The security policy is applied in general to the 5G verticals and potential use cases, and in particular to 5G testbeds infrastructure, but also to the Network Application and 3rd party applications. In this chapter, within the area of 5G the networks and applications, possible attacks, proposing the mitigation methods for the main 5G security concerns are evaluated, detailed in [50]. As a success of the VITAL-5G security implementation, by the moment of document preparation, **we faced no security or cybersecurity issues**. For clarity, by 3GPP the Core Network component for Control Plane are protected by TLS (Transport Layer Security), the Air Interface is encrypted (and integrity protected) between the device and the gNB, as **encrypted domains**, the transport network and the services Data Networks being protected by the design, using a suite of security methods and tools, as they will be mentioned later in the section. As the security functions are the heart of the 5G system, VITAL-5G provides endpoint security, slice security, cloud security and network security.

Figure 40: 5G network security testbeds implementation

5.1 Security approach in VITAL-5G

VITAL-5G defines several layers of security, adapted to a multi-level security architecture, based on 3GPP SA3 [51] security design aspects¹, for Security and Privacy, SA3 approach, seen in Figure 41:

- **Network Access Security;** Network Domain Security
- **User Domain Security; Application Domain Security;** SBA Domain Security
- **Visibility** and configurability of security

¹ <https://www.3gpp.org/3gpp-groups/service-system-aspects-sa/sa-wg3>

Figure 41: 5G SA3 security design, overview of security architecture

VITAL-5G infrastructures contains not only the 5G components, but also the **VITAL-5G platform**, exposed to (1) **partners**, (2) **developers** and further to the (3) other **3rd party experimenters**. The 5G security scenarios based on the EU risk report for the 5G networks are also evaluated, analyzing the different aspects as confidentiality, availability and integrity, presented in Figure 42, including -but not limited to- security accidental scenarios, individual hacker or group, state-backed door actor or inside a telco/5G testbed operator.

Figure 42: EU coordinated risk Threats, assets and vulnerabilities²

The main concerns for the security requirements within the VITAL-5G testbeds and developed application are required, treated and mitigated for the next components and functions:

- **Physical Infrastructure** (hardware equipment)
 - Physical hardware resources, computing, storage, network routers and switches.
- **Virtualized Infrastructure** (IaaS/CaaS)

² https://ec.europa.eu/commission/presscorner/detail/en/IP_19_6049

- Management systems, Hypervisor vulnerabilities, management interfaces/APIs; Northbound APIs interfaces, VNFs/VMs or CNFs attacks
- **5G Network Functions** (mainly the 5G RAN and Core)
 - Network configuration, exploitation of configured data, malicious functions.
- **Authentication and authorization**
 - Denial of services, essential core network access (e.g., UDM)
- **User data and signaling confidentiality and integrity**
 - Malicious functions to exploit signaling part
- **Secure storage and processing of subscription credentials**
 - Subscribers' privacy and data confidentiality

The security implementation is split in two major parts: (1) **5G network security** based on **3GPP** and **ENISA**³ cases and (2) VITAL-5G security implementation related to secured access to the **platform** and **testbeds** components (e.g. developer and 3rd parties' access in the system, protection of some exposed interfaces).

The testbeds are following the 3GPP security standards and implementation, in order to avoid or mitigate as much as possible the 5G network security issues. As described by [53] we are implementing the full set of security features and the security mechanisms of the 5G system following the security procedures performed within the 5G System (implementation by design).

Further mechanism related to 5GC core components, RAN (gNB level), UE, signaling and procedures can be seen in [54]. Virtualization is another important topic in 5G networks due to the NFV/VNFs implementation in the testbeds for the network components implementation or Network Application deployments, including services orchestration. We foresee several virtualization security requirements and implementation rules, from generic to specific NFVs threats, related to the next points and referred in detail in [55]. Currently describing, the 5G SA testbeds components are already in place, it has been followed the latest vendors software recommendation and upgrades, concerning not only to the system performance but also the security and vulnerability of the network elements, considering there have been implemented the latest software patches for issues mitigation.

The 2nd mentioned point related to the VITAL-5G security aspects, due to the complexity of the subject and the involvement of the project's partners, it considered to be detailed in a dedicated chapter, for sake of clarity, as follows in next section.

5.2 VITAL-5G security implementation

VITAL-5G security implementation is following the previously described activities and mitigation actions, by applying this concept for the VITAL-5G platform implementation and for the 5G testbeds.

In VITAL-5G we have identified several few security connectivity issues, mitigated through the next solutions, for the (1) **Platform Developers**, (2) **Testbed owners** in relation with the **VITAL-5G platform**, (3) **Network Application** developers and 3rd party experimenters that could run experiments on different VITAL-5G facilities and testbeds.

³ <https://www.enisa.europa.eu/>

For security reasons, there have been defined the security flows and isolation through routing instances for proper communication access to the different components, using IPSec VPNs Site2Site model or VPNs through SSL-VPNs model, as in Figure 43. The security configuration defined is then applied to all of VITAL-5G testbeds, ensuring proper isolation between all the actors, based on the security policy flows. Both presented methods (IPSec and SSL-VPNS) are highly scalable solution used in industry, using latest solution vendors providers, security tools⁴ for monitoring and threats identification, secured access to the platform or testbeds components to different security encryption models for the traffic (using tools from Fortinet Fortigate, Cisco ASA):

- **Site-to-Site VPNs** (VITAL-5G Platform hosted in ORO to the 5G testbeds for interfaces connectivity)
 - **Phase 1:** authentication methods with Pre-Shared Keys, encryption scheme IKEv2, Diffie-Helman Group 14 with 2048 bits, Encryption Algorithm AES-256, Hashing Algorithm SHA 256.
 - **Phase 2:** Encapsulation is Encapsulation Security Payload (ESP) for data confidentiality, data origin authentication, data integrity checking, and replay protection, using the same Encryption algorithms AES-256 and Authentication Algorithm SHA 256, by performing the **Perfect Forward Secrecy**, the encryption system that changes the keys used to encrypt the information frequently and automatically, protecting the session keys being compromised.

The Site-to-Site VPNs **pre-shared keys** are exchanged through an automatically keys exchange system, the VPN partner receiving the information through a valid SMS from an authorized entity inside ORO. The VPNs templates and the Keys are not exchanged through same emails, following the security recommendation for such activities, being impossible for an unauthorized user to access the system.

- **SSL VPNs** allows a developer or Network Application user to establish a secure, encrypted connection between the public internet and VITAL-5G Platform components and testbeds. The Secure Sockets Layer provide safe, secure communication via an encrypted connection for all types of devices, regardless of whether access to the network is via the public internet or another secure network.

Example of SSL VPN access is requiring the valid Name (Company), user email and Phone number for password SMS exchange.

In VITAL-5G we have created a **security by design** approach, as we are providing communication flows between different entities in a very controlled environment, strictly permitting only the access to the requested resources, on dedicated ports and to specific Sockets. Based on different security scenarios, all these accesses are permitted only using secured pre-shared keys for authentication, no others external entity being able to access any resources. As the Security Gateway for SSL or VPN are exposed in Internet, the Gateway and the system is protected by ORO security and cyber security systems from different attacks, as for example the most common attacks, as **DDOS, Malware, Phishing, Unauthorized access, Man in the Middle**.

⁴ <https://bis-threatmap.orange.ro/statistics>

Figure 43: VITAL-5G security access definition (users' groups)

Group Name	Group Type	Members
VITAL5G-Developers_USER_GROUP	Firewall	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> nextworks. [redacted] nextworks. [redacted] nextworks. [redacted] nextworks. [redacted] +24

Figure 44: Example of VITAL-5G users group definition for platform access.

It is concluded that the network and system attacks and threats are mitigated by using the security tools and products ORO has available, including but not limited to **AntiVirus, WebFiltering, Application Control, Intrusion Prevention, SSL/SSH inspection, Application Signature or IPS Signature**.

The security solution provides scanning of files and is blocking any viruses, all application being monitored and blocked if appropriate, preventing the attacks and identifying the applications.

The VITAL-5G security access rules permit the following flows detailed in Figure 43, as:

- **Platform software developers** to the VITAL-5G Platform VMs (RED flow),
- **Network Application developers** to the VITAL-5G Platform VMs and 5G testbeds (Blue Flow),
- **3rd Party Experimenters** to VITAL-5G Platform Components (Green Flow).

5.2.1 5G-Platform security aspects

VITAL-5G Platform is hosting of the software components described in WP2 [56], hosted in different VMs, accessed by the platform developers at this stage and implemented in the ORO Virtualized environment, for which we applied the security actions presented before, providing secured services for Network Application, Services & Experiments Catalogue, Portal Web GUI, Blueprint Validation Tool, Slice Inventory.

The architecture emulates and respects a fully functional next-generation **service provider** and **datacenter networks**, as this target architecture aims to solve a lot of the current technologies scalability, security and design issues that are commonly found in service provider and datacenters – among which the most important are the following: **Layers scalability, Recovery time** in case of failures, **redundant firewall** cluster for secure remote access and network security segmentation and servers running virtualization technologies (VMWare). We have defined a solution for the **PROD** and **DEV** virtualized environment for which we provided two separated tenants, **VITAL5G_PROD** and **VITAL5G_DEV**, as they

do not have direct communication between them, implemented through a multi-tenancy VITAL-5G Datacenter. Traffic between tenants in the Datacenter is separated by using the concept of VRFs (virtual routing instances), as this uses the technology described in RFC7432 [57] and uses Route Targets in order to logically separate the tenants in the datacenter.

In the proposed architecture, a **next-gen firewall** is present at the leaf layer in the Datacenter in order to secure both **east-west** and **north-south** flows, over all the architecture of the network security is as presented in the Figure 41.

The high-level description of the **network security architecture** is as follows:

- Two firewalls compose by an active-standby cluster for **High Availability** (HA) requirements
- The cluster is dual-attached to the IP Fabric system and uses dynamic routing with E-BGP sessions
- The cluster has 3 main interfaces (**DMZ** rules presented earlier):
 - **INSIDE** – towards the ORO network
 - **OUTSIDE** – towards the Internet (where the remote peers reside)
 - **DMZ** – where multiple, separated routing instances reside – where different tenant servers reside
- The Fabric architecture allows for **east-west** AND **north-south** traffic **filtering** with no additional interface configuration on the firewall
- Any secure external connectivity is concentrated in this redundant firewall cluster (be it IPsec site to site tunnel or Remote Access VPN)

Different secured and monitored traffic flows examples are seen in Figure 45, between different entities inside the cluster, as the non-legitim traffic is not allowed by policies.

Policy	Policy Type	Source Interface	Destination Interface	Bytes	Sessions
Access_internetDB (48)	Firewall	FW5GLAB-dmz-124	FW5GLAB-out-122	37.27 MB	8
beia-vm-to-mqtt-beia-site (37)	Firewall	FW5GLAB-dmz-124	FW5GLAB-out-122	28.32 MB	2
Access_Internet (1)	Firewall	FW5GLAB-dmz-124	FW5GLAB-out-122	8.61 MB	247
DNS Access (5)	Firewall	FW5GLAB-dmz-124	FW5GLAB-in-120	63.79 kB I	146
VITAL5G Servers to Internet (24)	Firewall	FW5GLAB-dmz-124	FW5GLAB-out-122	8.62 kB I	30
VITAL5G PROD and DEV to Openstack (40)	Firewall	FW5GLAB-dmz-124	FW5GLAB-dmz-124	2.60 kB I	26

Figure 45: VITAL-5G DMZ implementation and security policy definition

The two **PROD** and **DEV** tenants have connectivity via the firewall and every end-to-end flow is secured and **monitored** by the firewall cluster, described earlier. For example, it can be seen the legitimate traffic (green) and the policy violating traffic (red) in Figure 46.

The VITAL-5G Platform is protected for any external attacks (Firewalls, Cloud DDOS mitigation, logs), is deployed in a dedicated and isolated virtualized cluster, tenant hosting only the platform software components in different VMs, with controlled and secured access. For security reasons, the production environment of VITAL-5G platform is deployed in HA Mode, while software backups in protected storage clusters for new PROD software releases are performed. In a corner case when it is decided there are compromised or corrupted software components, from different reasons, the legitim software packages can be rebuild from the protected backups within minutes.

172.28.18.103	e4:1f:7b:2e:0d:07	213.227.185.133 (router15.teamviewer.com)		Deny: policy violation	Deny Teamviewer (42)
172.28.18.102	e4:1f:7b:2e:0d:07	172.28.22.181			VITAL5G PROD and DEV to Openstack (40)
172.28.18.103	e4:1f:7b:2e:0d:07	213.227.185.135 (router3.teamviewer.com)		Deny: policy violation	Deny Teamviewer (42)
172.28.18.102	e4:1f:7b:2e:0d:07	172.28.22.181			VITAL5G PROD and DEV to Openstack (40)
172.28.18.102	e4:1f:7b:2e:0d:07	172.28.22.181			VITAL5G PROD and DEV to Openstack (40)
172.28.18.103	e4:1f:7b:2e:0d:07	8.8.8.8 (dns.google)		✓ 87 B / 167 B	VITAL5G Servers to Internet (24)

Figure 46: Example of security logs for legitim traffic and policy violation

For clarity, ORO has performed security audits using internal security and cyber-security tools, testing the level of protection of the Platform, like unauthorized access, password attack. The final security reports are going to be integrated as internal security documents, if issues will be identified, corrections will be applied accordingly.

5.2.2 5G Testbeds' security implementation

The testbed owners are responsible for both the internal/external security aspects, based on the concepts detailed in Chapter 5.2, following the security and implementation standards and procedures for the 5G system, the virtualization environment and the secured access to the resources.

We have implemented security domains for each of these cases, considering the public interfaces exposed to the Internet that could be a potential security or cybersecurity breach. The scenario when a remote testbed could have a potential security issue or prominent to an attack that may impact the testbed has been also evaluated. Based on the 5G security implementation, we managed to avoid any potential vulnerabilities that can be faced due to illegitimate platform access from the other testbeds, based on **security filtering, cryptographic algorithms, authentication procedure, monitoring and isolation** within dedicated tenants with controlled limited access, there is not permitted any direct connectivity between the testbeds, but only between testbeds and VITAL-5G platform(IPSec VPNs), developers to testbeds or Platform(SSL VPNs).

For this scope, we provided two main external secure connectivity solutions, Figure 40:

- **Site to Site VPNs** – red dotted lines
 - Intended to interconnect platform to platform flows, standards-based IPsec suite using highly secure cryptographic algorithms like AES256 and SHA
- **Remote Access VPNs** – blue dotted lines
 - Intended for remote access teleworkers – used for Platform Developers secured remote access using SSL VPN with dynamic split tunneling feature.

Name	Source	Destination	Schedule	Service	Action	NAT	Security Profiles	Log	Bytes	ID
FW5GLAB-dmz → FW5GLAB-out 1/2										
VITAL5G Servers to Internet	IPF_DMZ_VITAL5G_DEV IPF_DMZ_VITAL5G_PROD	all	always	ALL_ICMP HTTP HTTPS DNS	ACCEPT	NAT_all,86.106.83.72	no-inspection	All	1.21 GB	24
SSL-VPN tunnel interface (ssl.fw-5GLAB) → FW5GLAB-dmz 1/2										
RA-VPN-VITAL5G-Developers to DMZ	VITAL5G-Developers.USER_GROUP RA-VPN-VITAL5G-Developers	IPF_DMZ_VITAL5G_DEV IPF_DMZ_VITAL5G_PROD	always	ALL_ICMP HTTP HTTPS SSH	ACCEPT	Disabled	no-inspection	All	174.91 kB	25
VITAL5G_OTE → FW5GLAB-dmz 1										
VITAL5G_OTE_TO_DMZ_VITAL5G	IPSEC_VITAL5G_OTE	IPF_DMZ_VITAL5G_DEV IPF_DMZ_VITAL5G_PROD	always	ALL_ICMP	ACCEPT	Disabled	no-inspection	All	504 B	23

Figure 47: VITAL-5G security flows sample

In addition, there are used advance security solutions for hot points as **Intrusion prevention, Web Filtering, IPAM, Application Control and Logs and Reports.**

The virtualized environment based on OpenStack implements for each of the testbed's security best practice implementation, guidelines that provides security OpenStack deployments. It is implemented the OpenStack authentication for the identity services, Keystone components through username and password protection, **TLS** services by using **X.509 certificates**, ensuring that only the authenticated users can access the system. OpenStack API endpoints are secured and isolated from the rest of the infrastructure.

Each valid user can access resources from the pre-defined tenant in the system, including secured and authenticated API communication between the Orchestrator (OSMv12) and OpenStack APIs.

6 VITAL-5G Facilities capabilities, network upgrades and implementation

The three testbeds are aligned with the target architecture since **December 2022**, while the integrations, testing and 5G SA experimentation has been already validated.

The 5G technical requirements of *Objective 2 (open, virtualized 5G-enabled testing and validation experimentation facility)*, benefit and showcase the added value of 5G connectivity of *Objective 3* and customized and virtualized access to network and T&L infrastructure of *Objective 4* are covered by this section. The testbeds and facility architecture are as described in Figure 48, by the date of deliverable submission, the testbeds are upgraded and integrated in the **targeted** design and **architecture**, running the **network slices**, where the **Network Applications** have been onboarded and experimented. Relevant achievements of the integration activities and results are presented in [69].

Figure 48: General view of VITAL-5G testbeds SA components

The enabled facility capabilities, through network upgrades and integration, available for different experiments, including the 3rd parties. In addition, VITAL-5G testbeds, running in High-Availability Mode, are implementing the necessary upgrades and extensions for the envisioned RAN, core and edge functionality (from Rel.15 to Rel.16), in order to deliver the 5G facility readiness for Network Application's, to deliver the open 5G-enabled virtualized testing and validation experimentation facility (see *Objective 2*) and to implement the 5G connectivity for advanced logistics services (see *Objective 3*):

- Extension of the existing 5G testbeds and integration of the new services orchestration
- VITAL-5G platform integration with the 5G testbeds
- 5G network slicing, provision of 5G services, concurrent slicing, multi-slice deployment
- 5G-NR, MEC capabilities, backhaul and core network technologies upgrades

The VITAL-5G testbeds are evaluated in terms of 5G network capabilities, focusing on 3GPP Rel.16, SA only, slicing/multi-slice implementation, virtualized infrastructure and 5G Security capable system.

The testbeds are 5G SA technology enabled, with different hardware or software components but providing the same functionalities, service slices capabilities, for example the **eMBB** slice (e.g., DL/UL 1200/120) and the **URLLC** slice (e.g. 5ms delay), the MEC capabilities and Virtualized Services (IaaS) to be

consumed by the Network Applications or 3rd party experimenters, as detailed in Table 11 for each of the testbeds.

The VITAL-5G testbeds offer the 5G SA technology features (including slicing, orchestration, traffic prioritization, monitoring), virtualized resources and the E2E service communication flow to experimenters, through a secured access to resources, flexible and adapted to the end-users needs.

Table 11: 5G network testbeds capabilities

Capabilities VITAL-5G Testbeds	3GPP 5G Release	5G RAN SA	5G Core NSA	5G Core SA	Network Slicing			MEC	Virtualiz ed Infra	5G Security
					eMBB (Mbps)	URLCC (ms)	mMTC (N/A)			
		Details	Details	Details				Details	IaaS/ CaaS	3GPP compliant
Galati Buchares t Testbed	Rel. 16	Yes Huawei Rel Nokia	Yes Ericsson Rel	Yes Nokia 21.1	Yes DL 1500 UL 150	1.5ms	N/A	Collocat ed with UPF	IaaS CaaS	Yes
Athens Testbed	Rel. 16	Yes Ericsson	Yes Ericsson/ Nokia	Yes Athonet Griffone	1000Mbps 100Mbps	5ms	complet ed/A	Justificati on provided in section 3.3.2	IaaS	Yes
Antwerp Testbed	Rel. 16	Yes Ericsson	Yes Nokia	Yes Nokia	Yes DL 1200 UL 120	Yes 5ms	500+	break out to Network Applicati on platform	IaaS	Yes

Furthermore, the available 5G resources of the testbeds are defined in terms of virtualization capabilities, VNFs available resources, used as templates by the Network Application developers or 3rd party experiments, service automation, monitoring and dashboards visualization, capabilities to expose the available resources to external partners and available resources to be consumed by the 5G UEs /slices, as depicted in Table 12.

Table 12: The VITAL-5G available resources

Capabilities VITAL-5G Testbeds	VNF capabilities (up to)			VMs/CNFs Total Number	Total Virtualized Infrastructure resources			MANO ETSI	Services	Monitoring capabilities	3rd Party Exposure
	Cores/ VNF	RAM/ VNF	Storage/ VNF		Concurrent VMs	CPU (vCPU)	RAM (GB)				
								Details Networ k Applica tions	Details	Details	Details

Galati/ Bucharest	16	32	40	200	3200	6400	8000	OSM Rel. 12 ⁵ K8s	Automation Network Service	Prometheus StableNet Graphana	5G Services VITAL-5G Platform
Athens	4	8	40	Currently 1	4	8	40	OSM Rel. 12	Network Service	Griffone	5G services
Antwerp	16	12	160	configurable	64	72	570	OSM Rel.12 K8s	Automation Network service	Prometheus Grafana	5G services

6.1 5G Slicing approach

The 5G slicing concept in VITAL-5G is similar for all three testbeds and it is technically implemented following the details presented in Section 2.5, as Figure 49 shows the model of implementing the end-to-end network slice based on the three different domains.

The slicing is implemented based on the 5G slice parameters, the S-NSSAI identifies network slices in NG-RAN and 5GC and is composed of a Slice Service Type (SST) and Slice Differentiator (SD), SST identifying a type of network slice with specific capabilities and characteristics and SD pointing out different network slices belonging to the same type, examples provided in Table 13.

Table 13: Service slice type/differentiator selection

Slice Name	Slice/Service Type	Slice Differentiator
NSSAI-1	1	abcdef
NSSAI-2	2	abcdea

While the network can support hundreds of slices, the UE need not support more than 8 slices simultaneously.

Figure 49: 5G slicing implementation in testbeds

There are several key principles that apply for supporting **network slicing** as **QoS differentiation** within a slice, resource management between slices, support for UE associating with multiple network slices

⁵ OSM version have been update to v12 for all three testbeds

simultaneously and **resource isolation between slices** (QoS Flow Identifiers) and service flow preservation through **5QI mapping** to transport **DSCP**, as depicted in Table 14.

At RAN level isolation and carrier isolation is performed, as detailed below:

- **Slice-level RB isolation:** Exclusive RBs are configured for services of a specific type of slice, realizing RB isolation among services of respective slices.
- **Slice-level carrier isolation:** A unique carrier serves UEs (in terms of camping or access) running services of a specific type of slice, realizing carrier isolation among services of respective slices.

Table 14: 5QI Translation Table

5QI	DSCP	GBR/non-GBR
1	EF (46)	GBR
2	AF31 (26)	
3	EF (46)	
4	AF32 (28)	
5	AF41 (34)	non-GBR
6	AF21 (18)	
7	AF22 (20)	
8	AF11 (10)	
9	BE (0)	

Moreover, the 5G SA slicing implementation and configuration are supported by the three testbeds, features and available results of slicing maturity as detailed in D3.2 [69], the South-bound Interface (SBI) of the VITAL-5G Platform enables its interaction with the VITAL-5G testbeds, functionalities described in Section 4.2. Through the VITAL-5G Platform requests, the testbeds are able to dynamically configure services within the existing preconfigured slice or to instantiate a new slice with respect of service request parameters, uniquely identified by the **SliceID**:

- "usedDataRateUL" (e.g., 20Mbps)
- "usedDataRateDL" (e.g., 100Mbps)
- "Latency" (e.g., 10ms)

The VITAL-5G testbeds implement in a similar way a novel slicing provisioning, offering to the final experimenters and developers several options for slice services usages: (1) to consume the existing slice, by attaching the end-user to the proper slice through the slice management interface, (2) to attach the service to a more appropriate slice or (3) to define a new service slice profile and to attach the end-user service to the newly implemented slice.

The three testbeds already have implemented, tested and validated the E2E slicing functionality, Network Application performing experiments through the service slice provisioning mechanism.

For the testbed's upgrades, the new 5GC interfaces are used, N3 and N6 interfaces for the **data plane** and N1, N2, N4, N8, N10, N11, N12 and N13 for the **control plane**, as summarized in Table 15, data plane and user plane separation brings another **security layer through design**.

Table 15: 5GCN 3GPP NF and interfaces⁶

Network Function	Peer Node/NF	3GPP Interface	Protocol
AMF	gNB	N2	NGAP/SCTP
	SMF	N11	HTTP2/TCP
	UDM	N8	HTTP2/TCP
	AUSF	N12	HTTP2/TCP
SMF	AMF	N11	HTTP2/TCP
	UPF	N4	PCFP/UDP
	UDM	N10	HTTP2/TCP
UPF	SMF	N4	PCFP/UDP
	gNB	N3	GTPv1/UDP
	DN	N6	IP
UDM	AMF	N8	HTTP2/TCP
	SMF	N10	HTTP2/TCP
	AUSF	N13	HTTP2/TCP
AUSF	AMF	N12	HTTP2/TCP
	UDM	N13	HTTP2/TCP

The three testbeds have already implemented, tested and validated the E2E slicing in the network, eMBB and URLLC slices, adapted to the Network Application services usage.

In VITAL-5G there are implemented slices as standalone private networks, by using private core network services connected to the RAN. Basically, a prioritized guaranteed QoS for services is provided over the 5G SA coverage, privacy and security through slices, answering to isolation and differentiated QoS, separated through a secured mobile network access (RAN, Core, Transport). By design, the testbed implements several combinations of network slices, as eMBB and URLLC, differentiated by the QoS profiles.

The secured routing in the 5G for proper slices end-points is ensured on a DNN basic using IP VPNs between UPFs and RAN accesses. In the setup described in Figure 50, different network slices are available in the testbeds to be consumed by the end user's services. One of the slices, (eMBB1) is a default shared slice for Internet connectivity, with a lower QoS prioritization, non-GBR, secured connected to the DNN Internet, the low QoS profile (5QI 9) is treated accordingly by the 5G testbeds as best-effort communication. Testbeds support more than one slice for eMBB and uRLLC, differentiated by the QoS/QI and slice profiles (eMBB1, eMBB2, uRLLC1). For example, it is configured an uRLLC network slice, 5QI configured 5 with a DSCP AF34, green DNN=C in the network which is securely connected to the proper Enterprise DC end-point (green one), for example a VM in the cloud.

⁶ <https://www.3gpp.org/technologies/5g-system-overview>

Figure 50: 5G examples of slices in the testbeds

In VITAL-5G the slices are isolated, dedicated network being allocated, guaranteeing the bandwidth requirements and delay budget for the services requirements. For example, the eMBB1 slice is considered a best effort slice, UL/DL throughput parameters **up to 1000/100 Mbps**, latency up to **40ms**, guaranteeing the connectivity to the service within some acceptable limits, to fulfill requirements of Internet access. The eMBB2 slice is a prioritized slice in terms of throughput, guaranteeing minimum connectivity throughput (e.g., **DL/UL 100/50 Mbps**), that in case of conflict with a lower priority slice, eMBB1, will always preempt lower priority slices. In a specific scenario, the uRLLC slice is always treated as high prioritized communication service, within low latency communication (e.g., **5ms**) and a guaranteed throughput (e.g. **UL/DL 20/10Mbps**), as this slice will preempt accordingly any others slices in the given network. Table 16 aggregates the VITAL-5G slices availability, for the possible shared slices or dedicated slices that can be consumed by the Network Application or 3rd party experimenters. For clarity, as previously described, the VITAL-5G infrastructure is capable of implementing network slices on demand, based on the application requirements, for example a communication service for intensive real time analytics and processing, as a uRLLC slice.

Table 16: VITAL-5G slices availability

Type	Slice	No. of slices in UE	Slice availability	Location access
Shared Slices	eMBBs	Mono slice	UE connects only to the mono slice	Everywhere or Restricted to enterprise
	eMBBs or uRLLC	Dual slice/Mono slice UE	UE can connect to either only one of the slices	
	eMBBs and uRLLC	Dual slice	UE can connect to both slices in the same time	
Dedicated slices	eMBBs or uRLLC	Mono slice	UE can connect to either only one of the slices	Restricted to enterprise
	eMBBs and uRLLC	Dual slice	UE can connect to both slices in the same time	

6.2 Evaluation of trials sites components

This chapter summarizes the testbeds and trials sites components available in the facilities, evaluating in fact what it has been reused for each testbed and trial facility from other projects/actions and mainly what it is developed and implemented as in the context of VITAL-5G.

For each trial site the 5G testbed and facility segment is analyzed, as well as relevant components and description of the status for each component. The testbeds trial site components and development are supported by several 5G-PPP previous projects, but due to the advanced requirements in terms of 5G Rel.16 capabilities, the testbeds implementation components are based on mainly new hardware, software and integration activities.

6.2.1 Galati (Danube) 5G trial site evaluation

In Galati (Danube), the 5G testbed and facility components have been implemented and upgraded, as depicted in Table 17.

Table 17: Galati (Danube) 5G trial site components evaluation

Trial site	Segment	Component	Justification	Status
Galati	5G Testbed	RAN	New gNodeBs both in Galati port and Orange Lab for losal testing. The gNB from Galati was first integrated in NSA mode, upgraded to SA fully 3GPP Rel 16 compliant from the second year of the project. 5G SA coverage in Galati. No Open RAN tools have been used due to the system stability requirements.	New
		Core	Dedicated 5G SA Core, 3GPP Rel. 16 compliant, a fully virtualized 5GCN, deployed in Bucharest facility and integrated also with the Galati gNB. 5G SA slicing No Open RAN tools have been used due to the system stability requirements	New
		Slicing	5G SA service slice implementation	New
		NFVI	NFVI newly built one, in HA architecture, using the virtualization environment software tools: Openstack Ussuri distributed cluster based on containers, ESXi VMWare cluster and Container Kubernetes cluster. OSM is connected to the Openstack VIM infrastructure, updated to OSMv12 VITAL-5G platform hosting	New and Extended
T&L Facilities		Vessel	NAVROM	Existing
		Sensors	5G gateway and several devices connected to the network, including a video camera, an AIS transponder, a depth sensor, engine and weather sensors.	Extended

6.2.2 Antwerp 5G trial site evaluation

In Antwerp, the 5G testbed and facility components have been implemented and upgraded, as described in Table 18.

Table 18: Antwerp 5G trial site components evaluation

Trial site	Segment	Component	Justification	Status
Antwerp	5G Testbed	RAN	The coverage requirement in Antwerp testbed includes large area over water, which is not possible to provide from the existing infrastructure upgrade. To make the multiple sailing routes and port infrastructure covered with 5G, high investment in new builds was necessary, along with as many upgrades as possible, including adjusted cell direction & tilting. Different 5G SA slicing design used in VITAL-5G and 5G-Blueprint.	New (Some existing sites utilized, but 2 new sites added)
		Core	New 5G SA network features deployment, with the focus on network-awareness features for Network Applications in VITAL-5G. On the other hand, the work with the Core functions used in 5G-Blueprint project is more focused on seamless roaming scenarios and development of missing features.	Existing (Existing Core, but new Core functions developed)
		Slicing	5G SA service slice implementation	New
		NFVI	Newly built NFV infrastructure for the purpose of the VITAL-5G project and creating the 5G edge (collocated with the 5G network aggregation point). This infrastructure is deployed both through OpenStack and Kubernetes, and is orchestrated by Open Source MANO v12.	New
	T&L Facilities	Vessel	Tercofin II, commercial vessel operated by Seafar. Partially used in the 5G-Blueprint project for the purpose of use case 1: Automated barge control, with two completely separate utilizations and partly different installations (Radar and GNSS used in VITAL-5G). Small boat in Port of Antwerp will be utilized for VITAL-5G live demos.	Existing
		Sensors	Seafar control system, GNSS receiver, one camera, 5G antenna, and radar used in VITAL-5G. The whole installation of sensors will be repeated for the small boat when preparing for live demos.	Existing

6.2.3 Athens 5G trial site evaluation

In the Athens, the 5G testbed and facility components have been implemented and upgraded, as seen in Table 19.

Table 19: Athens 5G trial site evaluation

Trial site	Segment	Component	Justification	Status
Athens	5G Testbed	RAN	A new gNodeB with two cells was installed in the Diakinisis warehouse premises. The coverage area is the pharmaceutical part of the warehouse. There is a similar setup for testing in OTE premises. Both gNodeBs are new equipment and are not carried out from the 5G-EVE project due to different use case requirements, licensing and support issues.	New
		Core	The Athens use case uses a new 5G Rel. 16 Core and a virtualized infrastructure which is different from the one used in the 5G-EVE project. This is due to control, licensing and support issues that prevented its re-use. The network infrastructure of the 5G-EVE, which have been under our own control, are reused. Network configuration and fiber optic cable installation had to be made to connect the 5G Core to the Diakisis warehouse.	New 5G SA Core, Network re-used
		NFVI	There are two virtualized infrastructures in the Athens testbed. The first infrastructure, managed by WINGS, reuses the server units that implement the Virtual Infrastructure. Dedicated tenant, project and user for VITAL-5G are created in the tools used. ETSI OSM v12 is deployed as a NFV Orchestrator, Openstack (Victoria release) as the Virtual Infrastructure Manager for VNFs, and Kubernetes v1.24.8 (microk8s deployment) for KNFs. The second infrastructure, used among others, for the deployment of the 5G SA packet core is totally new,	Updated
		5G slicing	5G SA slicing implementation	New
	T&L Facilities	AGV	Clearpath Boxer v2.4	New
		Sensors	Besides the AGV, a collection of surrounding fixed sensors and cameras will be mounted in a couple of locations within the warehouse (on the racks/shelves), referred to collectively as the Environmental Sensors pack, as they help monitor the warehouse environment. The pack will be comprised of the following sensors: Temperature sensor; Humidity sensor; Vibration sensor; Luminosity sensor and Full HD USB Camera. All the sensors are	New

			packaged together and connected to a Raspberry Pi which is used as an aggregation and communication gateway. The Sensor pack is also equipped with a 5G chipset to enable the connection of the environmental sensor pack to the 5G network and the transmission of the sensor and camera data over 5G connectivity, to the VITAL-5G platform. The AGV uses a RMU500EK Quectel board.	
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6.3 Galati (Danube) 5G-Testbed

6.3.1 Use case related requirements

The use case (UC#2) will be deployed in Galati, in order to highlight the benefits of using 5G networks for the management of information provided by river vessels. The two main modules that will interact directly and depend upon the 5G infrastructure are VS9, that will send information into the network (uplink), and VA9 that will provide a platform for the local access of the gathered information.

In VS9 we can distinguish 2 types of data traffic:

- Video streams of the ship's surroundings and/or interior.
- Sensors' data which consists of punctual parameters (position, depth, engine RPM, temperature, etc.)

The Video data will be obtained from cameras installed on the ship and the information provided does not represent standard navigation data, but will aim to enhance the standard and open the possibility for innovation in using data extracted from video streams to aid navigation.

The sensor data can be further divided into standard ship sensor data, and auxiliary sensor data. The standard ship sensor data will be obtained from standard equipment that is onboard the ship and is incorporated in current navigation practices. Auxiliary sensor data represents data collected for auxiliary purposes (smoke detection, general air quality, water quality) from additional sensors installed on the ship, such as temperature sensors, Ph sensors, carbon monoxide sensors.

In VA5 **the data collected** from VS9 will need to be made available to the navigation center. We can define the same requirements as in VS9.

Table 20: Network requirements for Network Application in use case 2 (1)

Traffic flow	Camera stream	Standard ship sensors data			Auxiliary sensor data	
		Water Depth	AIS	Engine	Water sensors	Air sensors
Service Type	Uplink	Uplink	Uplink	Uplink	Uplink	Uplink
Ideal Latency	<20ms	<100ms	<100ms	<100ms	<100ms	<100ms
Service Interruption	<30s	<1s	<1s	<1s	<1m	<1s

Bandwidth Requirement	10Mbps	<1kbs	<1kbs	<2kbs	<1kbs	<1kbs
Device Scenario	Outdoor/Indoor mobile	Indoor mobile	Indoor mobile	Indoor mobile	Outdoor mobile	Outdoor/Indoor mobile
Slice Type ⁷	URLLC	mMTC (eMBB)	mMTC (eMBB)	mMTC (eMBB)	mMTC (eMBB)	mMTC (eMBB)
No. Flow	1 per device	1 per ship			1 per device	

Some requests for different operation modes are necessary in the network but generally speaking most of the data is sent continuously to the testbed server and then made available to VA5. The requirements consider not only operation needs but also the level of importance for certain data. As such data that is non-critical (such as Ph levels in the water) can have more lenient requirements.

Table 21: Network requirement of Network Application in use case 2(2)

Traffic flow	Trajectory prediction/ variable forecasting UI	Remote Inspection & risk assessment UI
Network Application	VA2	VA3
Service Type	Downlink	Downlink
Ideal Latency	<100ms	<100ms
Service Interruption	<15s	<15s
Bandwidth Requirement	>5Mbps <50Mbps	>5Mbps <50Mbps
Device Scenario	Indoor stationary (could also apply for Outdoor/ indoor mobile)	Indoor stationary (Outdoor/ indoor mobile)
Slice Type	eMBB	eMBB
No. Flow	1 per UE	1 per UE

⁷ mMTC slice is not implemented in the testbed, the service is supported by eMBB slice

6.3.2 Network infrastructure capabilities and site facilities upgrades

The VITAL-5G target architecture is a 3GPP Rel. 16 [7], **5G SA implementation**, following the required extensions and upgrades on to the testbed with the proper RAN/Core/Edge, equipment and infrastructure in order to support within the testbed the hardware, software and platform integration. In this section only, the extension of the infrastructure and upgrades required, on-top of the already defined infrastructure in Chapter 3, is presented.

The 5G site deployed in Galati for VITAL-5G Romanian use-case is a Huawei gNodeB integrated in a first stage in 5G RAN2.1 software release. This release is 3GPP Rel 15 compliant, meaning the majority of 3GPP Rel15 features are available. Nevertheless, 5G SA is available in this release but as described in Chapter 3, with limited functionality. In order to enable E2E slice roll-out, RAN slicing is mandatory, requiring upgrade to next release compatible with 3GPP Rel 16 specifications. Therefore, the 5G site from Galati was upgraded to target software release in Q4 2021, hence unlocking also other Rel16 benefits as enhanced MIMO performance, reduced UE power consumption, reduced control plane processing delays due to two-step RACH procedure. [58]

The following paragraphs offer a brief description on RAN slicing concept, as presented in [59]. Slice resources are controlled on the RAN to offer differentiated policies for slice UEs.

The NG-RAN identifies slices through basic protocol-defined slicing procedures. Specifically, the RAN identifies slice UEs based on the Single Network Slice Selection Assistance Information (S-NSSAI) of services running on the UEs and performs differentiated processing.

The 5G testbed core used in Galati is a fully virtualized 5GCN, deployed in Bucharest facility and integrated also with the Galati gNB, in the SA option 2 architecture.

Figure 51: 5GCN Solution Architecture

The testbed design provides the following 5G core network functions, as presented in Chapter 2:

- AMF (Access and Mobility Management Function)
- SMF (Session Management Function)
- UPF (User Plan Function)
- UDM (Unified Data Management)
- AUSF (Authentication Server Function)
 - authentication for 3GPP access as specified in [53]

Based on the updated 5G SA Core deployment effort (SBA), in line with 3GPP standardization, see Figure 9, new interfaces have been implemented (SBIs).

In our 5G deployment, the 5GCN network is possible to be divided into multiple logical networks, called “slices”, as described in Chapter 2. In this context, for each of the slices (2 network slices) we are able to perform the optimization of the network services: 1st network service slice is the eMBB and 2nd service slice is the Ultra-Low-Latency communication, as presented in Figure 4. The virtualization layer is implemented during the 5G testbed upgrades and extensions action within VITAL-5G, with the scope of creating a virtualized environment to run the 5G Network Applications and related functions, 5G Core network components and the VITAL-5G platform hosting. The testbed has also been extended and upgraded to support not only the different virtualization tools and orchestration techniques (as Openstack), but also the VITAL-5G Openstack deployed in the testbed is integrated as VIM with the OSM, within the VITAL-5G tenant, as all the resources available in the project are allocated to the VITAL-5G applications, mainly for the Network Application developments and onboarding in the infrastructure. The extension of the testbed capabilities will also be used for 3rd party applications, VNFs or CNFs that could further be deployed in the testbed, as detailed in Figure 52.

Figure 52: VITAL-5G OSM tenant implementation

In order to provide the end-to-end network slicing, we have identified the need to implement the proper network slicing and configuration also in the IP/Transport network. The architecture of the transport network is presented in Figure 22, main testbed network components as presented in Chapter 3. As presented, the entire network configuration and proper resources allocation for QoS, as per slice network implementation, is performed by manually adding the ensuring the network resources to each traffic flow. It is required to implement, from the transport network perspective, the E2E Network Orchestrator, a network orchestrator that handles services deployment, instantiation and chaining for reliable and fast deployment of network services.

We conclude that the testbed should be extended and upgraded with the implementation of a network orchestrator tool, orchestrator that offers, in the 5G context, the following functionalities:

- Standards-based northbound and southbound communication channels
 - GUI-based HTTPS, SSH CLI and RECONF + NETCONF for Northbound from other orchestrators (e.g. MANO/ONAP) and Network Admins
 - SSH and NETCONF for Southbound device stream
- Service lifecycle implemented; Standards-based YANG and XML used for business logic design and device templates
- Available python or java scripting for computation of service resources; Support CRUD (Create, Read, Update, Delete) operations from day 1

In the Romanian testbed of VITAL-5G we have identified the major hardware and software upgrades and integration needs to support the main capabilities and network features keys to respond to the 5G Network Application deployment, covering the 5G RAN, Core, Transport, Virtualization and Orchestration, extending the infrastructure to support also VITAL-5G Platform. The testbed monitoring is envisioned to the upgrade from the monitoring perspective, pointing several main data sources, from the 5G RAN, Core, Transport and Virtualization area, as in Table 22:

Table 22: Orange testbed monitoring system

Radio	Core	Transport	Monitoring
5G SA traffic volumes	5G SA Core REST service	Troubleshooting	Grafana
5G SA Call Setup	list of alarms	ports, interfaces, LSPs	monitoring tool
5G SA Drop Call	root cause/impacts	link utilization	Internal tools
Average reported CQI	tree causes/impact for a specific alarm	latency optimization	
Average number of Users	network performance	TCEs on errors, discards, utilization	
Physical resource Blocks Load	monitor in real-time or periodically	IP traffic usage	
5G SA average user throughput			

6.3.3 Facility Equipment

All connections and sensor terminals (for depth - Actisens DST 2, for video cameras - Hikvision DVR, for CAT engines - Caterpillar BUS BUS) are positioned in the ship's cockpit (wheelhouse), and connection with 5G terminals is relatively easy. The type of connection supported by these equipment's is serial 232 or 485 respectively NMEA 0183 or NMEA 2000. The design is the one specific to the industrial equipment's. The 5G equipment will be installed in the wheelhouse, where there are also terminals from the ship's equipment. Also, here is the highest place of the ship where there are no obstacles in the GSM radio transmission between the ship and the Orange terrestrial relays.

Figure 53: Type of vessel which is involved in UC 2

Figure 54: 5G NSA/SA Validated 5G Router

The equipment's and sensors from the ship that will be connected to the 5G interface are the following:

- DVR (Digital Video Recorder)
- Video cameras (HD)

Few HD and Full HD cameras are distributed throughout the ship, in the engine room, wheelhouse, exterior, etc.

Figure 55: DVRs and Camera

- Ultrasonic depth equipment è it measures water depth, which has a piezo-type thru-hull sensor DT 505, DST-2 digital analog interface (Depth, Speed, Temperature) on 200 kHz single or multiple pulse and IS-20 display from Simrad, the connection is made by RS 232 serial connection.

Figure 56: Depth Sensors, Interfaces and depth display

- CAN-BUS port in the engine computer.

The information collected from Caterpillar type propulsion engines is obtained through the existing CAN-BUS port in the engine computer. These refer to real-time data on engine speed, load, temperature, pressure.

Figure 57: Propulsion engine and engine calculator schematic

The GPS position information of the vessel is provided by the AIS transponder equipment. It consists of a GPS antenna with a precision less of 5 m, that gives us in real time the position of the ships (LONG, LAT) and a VHF antenna that can connect with the other ships around within a range of up to 32 km. Also, information from this equipment we can have information about speed, trajectory, destination, ship and ships in the area, in real time, the connection with 5G terminals is also done via RS 232 serial.

Figure 58: Ship position, speed and trajectory.

(a AIS transponder (b Diagram AIS connection

Figure 59: AIS transponder and diagram AIS connection

From all these devices, the data transfer to the 5G router will be done by shielded cable and / or fiber optics.

6.3.4 Facility Planning

The VITAL-5G Galati planning is based on the use case requirements analysis, 5G technology deployment, targeting 5G Rel.16, system components upgrade and extensions and testbed implementation in the field, as seen in Figure 60. Based on the planning, starting with mid-H1 2022, the 5G SA is available also in the Galati port, network slicing implementation, eMBB and ULLC, service slice being available for the Network Application, within the E2E scenario of the deployment, multi-slice experimentation and facility validation.

Figure 60: Galati facility planning 2022

Figure 61: Galati facility planning 2023

6.4 Antwerp 5G-Testbed

6.4.1 Use case related requirements

As mentioned in deliverable D1.1 [67], the 5G technology for Network Application in Use case 1 can be defined in three type of services:

- Slice Type 1 Aggregated data collection: an eMBB network slice focus on high performance and relatively low latency and high reliability for video streaming and sensor data sharing. Note that the data could be both uplink data towards centralized cloud, or uplink + downlink data sharing between agents.
- Slice Type 2 Vessel controls: an URLLC network slice to ensure vessel control, either from remote vessel operator or automated by Network Application.
- Slice Type 3 Dedicated small sensor: an MTC slices supporting varies type of sensor with mobility on vessel of land infrastructure. These sensors could be added in large quantity as port infrastructure develops and remain flexible to bring online

For each traffic flow defined by Network Application, following specification are used, per flow:

Table 23: Network Application traffic flow

Video

Description	Resolution	Frame rate	Bandwidth
SD Video	858 x 480 pixels	<u>30 fps</u>	<u>3 Mbps</u>
HD Video	1920 x 1080 pixels	<u>30 fps</u>	<u>5 Mbps</u>
UHD Video	3860 x 2160 pixels	<u>30 fps</u>	<u>25 Mbps</u>

Video encoding and decoding process normally take less than 3ms. The MPEG and H.264 Video codec are resilient to delay and variance of this delay. From the encoder/decoder perspective the maximum allowable technical delay is more than one second. Thus, the application only sets the overall requirements for delay and jitter, not specifically the video codec.

Table 24: Delay and Jitter requirements

Audio

Coding type	Description	Bandwidth	Latency
G.711	Non-Compressed Voice	64 kbps	< 200 ms delay (E2E)
G.726	ADPCM Codec	40, 32, 24, 16 kbps	< 200 ms delay (E2E)
AMR-WB	3GPP codec	23.85 – 6.6 kbps	< 200 ms delay (E2E)

Table 25: Telemetry requirements

Telemetry [3]

Data source	Description	Bandwidth	
RADAR	0,1 – 15 Mbps/sensor	15	Mbps
Ultrasonic	per sensor	< 15	kbps
A-GPS	Vehicle motion, IMU...	< 100	kbps
CAN	ISO 11898-3	125	kbps
CAN/CAN-FD	ISO 11898-2	5	Mbps
CAN-XL	under development	10	Mbps

The result of the Network Application requirement analysis is described in Table 26.

Table 26: Network requirement of Network Application in use case 1

Traffic flow	HD Camera feed	HD video screens	Ship control interface	Sensor data on board	Other sensor data
Network Application	VA4, VS5	VA4, VS5	VS5, VS6	VS6, VS7	VA4, VS6, VS7
Service Type	Uplink	Downlink	E2E	Uplink	Uplink
Ideal Latency	<22ms	<22ms	<35ms	<100ms	<100ms
Service Interruption	<30s	<30s	<150ms	<1s	<1s
Bandwidth Requirement	>5Mbps <25Mbps	>5Mbps <25Mbps	<2Mbps	<1Mbps	<1Mbps
Device Scenario	Outdoor mobile	Outdoor stationary	Outdoor mobile + Outdoor stationary	Indoor mobile	Outdoor mobile + Outdoor stationary
Slice Type	eMBB	eMBB	URLLC/ hMTC	V2X	IoT
No. Flow	10 per ship	6 per operator	1 per ship	1 per ship	1 per device

As shown in table above, each type of use case traffic is identified. According to the description of traffic flow, “HD camera feed” refers to a single stream of camera data, and “HD video screens” refers to a single stream of camera feed towards teleoperation center.

“Service Type” only describes the main radio service involved for the data flow. Similar to “From/To” info, in practice all data flows require both downlink and uplink radio services. The information here only describes the main radio service type to highlight the boundary and focus of the 5G radio network in different cases. For example, the control data is first uploaded from Teleoperation Centre by 5G network then downloaded to Teleoperated Vehicle by 5G network. Thus, the URLLC/hMTC service is defined as end-to-end. For HD camera feed, in normal situation, the camera data flow is uploaded by 5G network and sent to Teleoperation Centre via fixed network, thus radio service is identified as “Uplink”.

“Ideal Latency” describes the network latency threshold defined by use case owners. Latency for use case traffic is always the lower the better, but the value described here is sufficient to unlock the full potential of the service based on existing use case hardware and software. Note that the value needs to be considered together with “Service Type”. For example, the “<35ms” latency of ship control interface refers to E2E latency with both uplink and downlink. While “<22ms” of video stream data refers to uplink and downlink separately, resulting in E2E latency of <45ms.

“Service Interruption” describes the allowed network interruption time of one single traffic stream, NOT the complete traffic type. This is a strong use case dependent value. For example, the allow interruption time of one camera stream is “<30s”, which is very relaxed for tele-operation. There are 10 cameras generating 10 camera streams on one vessel, while the tele-operator only supervises 6 camera views on screen simultaneously, some redundancy is already considered by camera setup on vessels. Such redundancy is not only in place for network interruptions, but also considering the rough environment that camera operates on vessels and the multi axis movement of vessels.

“Bandwidth Requirement” is the range of required 5G bandwidth of one data flow.

“Device Scenario” describes the general environment where the 5G UE will be installed. This will have a direct impact of field strength requirement of the 5G signal. “Outdoor mobile” refers to 5G UE is normally installed in an outdoor environment with outdoor antenna, and the UE is on mobile which leads to potential handovers or roaming. “Outdoor stationary” is similar to “Outdoor mobile” while the UE is stationary at a fixed location. “Indoor mobile” is considered in case location of sensors are deep inside the vessel, and cabling towards an 5G UE outdoor is not applicable, thus signal penetration into vessel cabinet is considered. It does not necessarily mean the 5G UE cannot be equipped with outdoor protection and outdoor antenna for better antenna gain.

“Slice Type” is a general identification of the type of network slice according to 3GPP standard.

“No.Flow” refers to the number of data flows of the described data flow type of the use case, which leads to the maximum number of flows supported by one 5G device.

6.4.2 Network infrastructure capabilities and site facilities upgrades

The complete 5G testbed in the Antwerp trial site consists of the 5G SA network infrastructure, i.e., 5G RAN and 5G Core, and virtualized infrastructure deployed on the IMEC premises. This testbed is visually presented in Figure 62, while in this Section we focus on the orchestration implementation for the virtualized infrastructure. The computing infrastructure is provided for hosting Network Application, which are designed and developed in WP2.

The virtualized infrastructure supports both Open Source MANO (OSM) and Kubernetes as orchestration solutions, whereas Kubernetes one is an extended version of native Kubernetes that supports an

enhanced decision-making process for various orchestration operations, such as instantiation, scaling, migration, and termination.

Figure 62: The 5G testbed in the Antwerp trial site.

In general, if performed in an automated way, the management and orchestration of virtualized infrastructure and services consists of the three phases: i) orchestration, ii) control, and iii) monitoring. Regardless of their distinctive features, these three phases are significantly dependent on each other, and their ultimate goal to improve the whole service management and orchestration process.

From the perspective of an automated closed-loop life-cycle management, such an architectural framework is illustrated in Figure 64, showcasing the way we grouped the important architectural elements into the orchestration, control, and monitoring categories [60].

In general, the overall monitoring process has to ensure that each Network Application is running properly, by extracting the critical information from the physical or virtual nodes (i.e., network functions, links, etc.), and sending important notifications to the orchestration and control entities. It comprises data collection and information extraction, which are directly performed by monitoring entity shown in Figure 63 and Figure 64, i.e., Prometheus, Grafana, and Zenoh [61] framework. The extracted information is further leveraged by orchestration plane which makes corrective decisions. Afterwards, the control entity performs the actions implied from the orchestration decisions, which might include resource re-arrangement, VNF/service migration, scaling, and terminating.

For the tested setup, we use the research testbed at IMEC, which is a large-scale generic environment for advanced networking, distributed software, cloud, big data, and scalability research and testing. In overall, the testbed contains several bare metal and GPU servers which are fully configurable in terms of their software installation, as well as the interconnection between network interfaces. Regarding connectivity, each node has a public IPv6 address as well as public IPv4, and thus can be easily accessible from any machine inside or outside of testbed environment. As nodes can be utilized for wide variety of purposes (such as terminal, server, network node, and impairment node), we used three of them to install OpenStack, as virtualization infrastructure, altogether with Kubernetes and OSM (Figure 64).

Figure 63: Mapping ETSI NFV MEC components to the 5G testbed solution

Figure 64: Design choices for virtualized infrastructure in the Antwerp 5G testbed

Concerning Kubernetes deployment, we provide the NFV infrastructure in various hosts by virtualizing computational resources of underlying computing machines. This orchestration solution is quite portable, as we deployed it at several testbeds on IMEC premises, and some of the Proof-of-Concepts (PoC) that we built are presented in several scientific publications[61] [62]. For instance, we presented the collocation of MEC platforms with Road-Side Units (RSUs) in [63], and used it in the demo setup for emergency Vehicle-to-Everything (V2X) services in [64] (without any exclusive orchestration design for V2X services,

thus, making it able to orchestrate any type of service/application). To make use of the computational resources for performing lifecycle management of network applications, we deploy Kubernetes (K8s), where orchestrator embodies the role of K8s master and extends to support some additional features, such as Artificial Intelligence (AI)-enhanced support for decision-making, and cross-NFV domain operations. Such K8s master with extended and enhanced operation deploys services and applications on designated worker nodes. In the PoC, both master and worker nodes can be deployed on the bare metal, as well as in Linux containers (LXC), which is a more suitable practice for shared experimentation environments as testbeds. For each type of data that is collected, i.e., computational and network resource utilization, energy consumption, KPIs measured at users' side, and users' locations, we also deploy MEC value-added services, as per definition in ETSI MEC [65], which perform data retrieval and pre-processing before publishing them on Zenoh. Given its minimal network overhead (as little as 5B), and its small footprint (around 60kB on Arduino board), Zenoh is adopted in our PoC as a framework for data engineering pipeline. In particular, Zenoh provides a minimal set of primitives to deal with data in motion (e.g., real-time stream of UE location/speed/destination), data at rest (e.g., historic data for UE's and computing nodes' computational resource utilization and energy consumption) and remote computations (e.g., on-demand calculation of the best route for the vessel and speed limit) [66]. Orchestrator acts as a subscriber for various types of data that can be stored on computing nodes, and used for training or online learning/optimization.

RAN upgrades: In Phase 2 all RAN equipment will be swapped to Ericsson for 5G and legacy technology.

Note that the 5G SA cells are configured on the shared RAN equipment but logically separated. As the production network has very limited 5G usage, the interface between testbed network and production network is very low. The current designed upgrade is also excluding 700MHz band. If 700MHz band becomes available, further upgrade can be easily added. So 5G UE will attach to N1, N78 or N1 + N78 in CA mode for network slicing. In case 700MHz spectrum is available, it can also operate alone or in CA mode with N78.

MEC upgrades

The general advantages of edge computing include a lower latency, relieving network load in the core networks, and potentially keeping data locally for security/privacy reasons (isolation). There are multiple options to deploy distributed cloud or edge solutions, including:

- Edge computing at MNO data center; Edge computing at Mobile Edge
- Edge computing at Network Application platform; Distributed computing over Device, Edge, and cloud
- Edge Computing and RAN split in Central and Decentral Units

As mentioned in Section 3.2.1, the last two options are not applied in Antwerp testbed.

Edge computing at MNO data center

The computing power for the application platform could be located in the same data center where UPF for user plane data is terminated. In this case, the cloud infrastructure of MNO can be utilized to provide service to consumers with lower latency and data insulation. This solution can be considered for this Antwerp testbed but may reduce the flexibility of Network Application development.

Edge computing at mobile edge

Local processing equipment could be provided at the cell tower itself, leading to even lower latencies and keeping user data extremely localized. This equipment would still be completely part of the operator

network/management and hence can potentially be used for several customers at the same time. Due to the high costs, the complexity in management, limited space and power at the sites, and distributed computing power requirement from use cases, this is not the best solution for Antwerp testbed.

Edge computing at Network Application platform

In this solution the UPF can be directly connected to the local customer data center via a regional breakout solution. In case of Antwerp testbed, the use cases have existing computing power and operation centers where data can be reached from public network. A region breakout point close to Antwerp testbed can be used to provide direct connection towards the use case owners via fiber ring of fixed line. This is the most suitable edge solution for Antwerp testbed.

The typical delay contributions of the different components in two Edge computing scenarios are shown in Figure 65.

Figure 65: Example of delay contribution in edge deployment scenarios

The top route is edge computing at operator data center and the bottom branch encompasses a local break-out of the User Plane traffic to a local instance of the UPF at the site router. As illustrated above, there are more possible paths and thus possible values of the delay in the top branch. This causes the variance in delay to be larger than in the bottom branch.

Core upgrades:

In phase 2 the Nokia CMU core solution is deployed to provide 5G SA core. At initial deployment following core network elements are included, and more elements to enable with software upgrade during the project to support full function of 3GPP defined 5G core as shown in Figure 66.

Figure 66: Nokia CMU of phase 2 initial deployment

Network slices

As discussed in Table 26 a slicing design is made based on the requirement. The E2E slicing will be implemented in Antwerp testbed by using GSMA generic network slicing template NG.166.

Transport Upgrades

As mentioned, the transport network in Antwerp testbed is shared with production network and logically separated. All transmission network used for VITAL 5G are fiber based and terminated in Telenet data center in Aartselaar, which is 20km away from Port of Antwerp, with additional headend for possible local break out for MEC and distributed UPF. Due the network is shared with production network, topology of transmission network cannot be shared. The high-level illustration of the upgrade is as following:

Figure 67: Transport network upgrades of Antwerp testbed

Network security Upgrades

In phase 2 upgrade as RAN and transport is shared with production network, network security policies (such as IPsec) and firewall rules are implemented the same as production network.

With such firewall policy the traffic source, traffic type and traffic destination are well protected and monitored. Additional security system can be implemented, if necessary, e.g., for IoT data without sufficient application layer security.

- Device can only connect to gateway via secure, private VPN tunnel; Authentication via IMSI using RADIUS.
- Cloud Gateway; Secure bridge with data encryption between devices and IoT Hub.
- Protocol translation enabling secure bi-directional communication.
- Deployed on Service Fabric, provisioned inside the Private VNET of Telenet.
- Device Authentication between Cloud gateway to IoT Hub using Symmetric keys.
- Gateway to Hub communication is encrypted (AMQP with SAS); Public end points at gateways are limited and HTTPs encrypted.

Monitoring and network KPIs

In phase 2 the network monitoring tools are also upgraded. The target is to provide a full evolution of network KPIs with both data directly exposed from network and 3rd party monitoring devices (such as network analyzing UEs).

6.4.3 Facility Equipment

A typical 5G UE packaged with IP67 casing and external antenna is used in use case 1 for the maritime environment.

Figure 68: Pepwave BR1 Pro 5G for Antwerp testbed

Note that the device is installed with trial firmware to support network slicing. The 5G UE is supposed integrate with existing cable network on board. Some key features of this 5G UE are listed below:

- WAN Interface: 1x 10/100/1000/2500M Ethernet, 1x 5G Modem with Redundant SIM Slot
- LAN Interface: 2x 10/100/1000M Ethernet/Wi-Fi Interface: Wi-Fi 6, 2X2 MU-MIMO
- Router Throughput: 1Gbps; 5G Cellular Data Rate4 (Downlink/Uplink): 4Gbps / 700 Mbps
- 5G bands: n1, n2, n3, n5, n7, n8, n12, n20, n28, n38, n41, n66, n71, n77, n78, n79

Concerning the facility equipment, the Tercofin II vessel will be used for this project (110m long, 11.4m wide), as it could be seen in Figure 69. This vessel contains a Global Navigation Satellite System (GNSS) device, cameras, and radar unit, which are all available for usage in the project. A Hemisphere GNSS installation is available for retrieving the usual latitude/longitude values, but data such as the heading, pitch, speed, altitude can be also accessed via this device. The initial plan is to provide the recorded data for any interested parties, whereas for the actual demo we are currently considering the ways to send the data in a secure way to the respective partners or their Network Application.

Figure 69: Tercofin II vessel that is being used in the Antwerp trial site

Figure 70: Tercofin II camera setup

Figure 71: Programmable Logic Controller

6.4.4 Facility Planning

The testbed upgrade started from Q4 2021, starting with dismantling of 5G equipment from the phased-out vendor. The roadmap of phase 2 deployment is mentioned in Section 3.1 and details as following:

On RAN side:

- The first step is to validate RAN swapping and building methodology with Ericsson. And evaluate the performance of test sites. This was done by three 5G cell towers neighbouring Port of Antwerp as shown in figure below. The validation was finished in Feb 2022.

Figure 72: RAN validation 5G sites for Antwerp testbed

- Step two is to deploy RAN in Port of Antwerp area, which will be finished by end of April 2022.
- Step three is to integrate connectivity from Antwerp testbed towards testbed core located in Aartselaar, which will be finished by end of May 2022.
- The last step is to implement network security rules between production RAN environment and Antwerp testbed environment and validate the E2E connectivity. This is expected by end of June 2022.

On the Core side:

- The first step is to provide high level design, including features selection for Antwerp testbed core network. This is expected by Feb 2022.
- Step two is to provide low level design for connectivity requirements, including interface and IP design between RAN and Core, etc. This step is expected by April 2022.
- Step three is for installation of core network hardware. Expected end of April 2022.
- Step four is for commissioning and configuring the core network for Antwerp testbed. Expected by June 2022.
- The last step is for RAN & core integration for E2E connectivity test. Expected by end of June.

As 5G connectivity is ready the Antwerp testbed is ready for E2E trials. Details of actions in Antwerp testbed is described as below. Note that dry runs before July 2022 are based on 4G connectivity or other existing connectivity to test basic signaling and functionalities of developed Network Application.

Figure 73: Antwerp testbed planning 2022

The initial planning of 2023 is described in Figure 74:

Figure 74: Antwerp testbed planning 2023

Note that at end of 2022 or beginning of 2023, an upgrade on testbed is performed to support features of 3GPP R16.

6.5 Athens 5G-testbed

6.5.1 Use case related requirements

The UC#3 trial will be performed in Attica region, close to the city of Athens, aiming at to demonstrate the feasibility of applying the 5G technology in an overall Logistics context, for optimizing warehousing operations. The trial site is a part of the DIAKINISIS Warehouse “Imeros Topos”, specifically the pharmaceutical part of an overall are of 1.200 m², as previously depicted in Figure 30, where the RAN part of the network will be installed. In this area, all the Warehouse operations will be taking place assisted by certain devices (incl. AVG, Raspberry Pi, environmental sensors) and supported by 5G network as already mentioned.

As specified in section 3.3.1 the Greek testbed architecture will be based on the 5G-EVE Greek testbed, which is implemented and tested successfully. The 5GC will be installed in OTE’s premises in Marousi. The distance between Diakinisis and OTE premises is about 25km.

UC#3 targets the following:

- Lean warehousing: Elimination of time "wastes" in various warehousing operations, such as movements from picking to checking area and put-away operation. The great benefit of AGVs lies in replacing non-value labour and equipment (forklifts) in an operation (Network Application VS1).
- Route optimisation for order picking considering heterogeneous data sources, such as products location, FIFO/FEFO rules, location of employees, final destination of order, product type, sensor data (e.g., humidity, temperature), etc. (Network Applications VS1, VA1).
- Availability of remote surveillance and monitoring of processes as well as remote override and handling by human operator. Enabled by multiple UHD streams requiring an eMBB slice (Network Applications VS1, VS2).
- Advanced AGV operations enabled by 5G connectivity, allowing obstacle / human avoidance, cooperation with human operators (“follow-me function”) and collaboration with other automated moving vehicle (URLLC aspects) (Network Applications VS1, VS2).

Detailed presentation of UC#3 is included in [67].

As mentioned also above, the 5G technology for Network Applications in Use case 3 can be defined in two types of services:

- Slice Type 1 Aggregated data collection: an EMBB network slice focus on high performance and relatively low latency and high reliability for video streaming and sensor data sharing. The data in this case are uplink data towards the centralized cloud platform (WINGSChariot in this case) but in other cases both uplink and downlink data can be required i.e., in a scenario where we have more than one AGV performing a collaborative task within the warehouse.
- Slice Type 2 AGV controls: an URLLC network slice to ensure allowing obstacle / human avoidance, cooperation with human operators (“follow-me function”) and collaboration with other automated moving vehicles.

For **each traffic** flow defined by the Network Application, the following specifications are used, per flow:

Table 27: Video Network Application flow

Description	Resolution	Frame rate	Bandwidth
VGA Video	640 x 360 pixels	<u>30 fps</u>	<u>5 Mbps</u>

HD Video	1280 x 720 pixels	<u>30 fps</u>	<u>23 Mbps</u>
FHD Video	1920 x 1080 pixels	<u>30 fps</u>	<u>50 Mbps</u>

Table 28: Telemetry station requirements

<u>Data source</u>	<u>Description</u>	<u>Bandwidth</u>
RPI (Temperature, Pressure, Humidity)	<u>Per station</u>	< 1 kbps

Table 29: AGV requirements

<u>Data source</u>	<u>Description</u>	<u>Bandwidth</u>
Lidar	Laser scan sensor	1 Mbps
Location	AGV location sensor	1 Mbps
Battery	Batter percentage	< 1 kbps
Diagnostics	Multiple AGV diagnostics	< 1 kbps
Follow Me Distance	AGV distance from person	< 1 Mbps
Follow Me Controller State	Follow me controller state	< 1 kbps
RSSID	RSSID measurement	1 Mbps
State	AGV current state	< 1 kbps
Velocity	AGV velocity	< 1 kbps

The result of the Network Applications requirements analysis is described in Table 30.

Table 30: Network requirement of the Network Applications in use case 3

Traffic flow	HD Camera feed (AVG)	HD video screens (Telemetry)	AGV	Other sensor data (Telemetry station)
Network Application	VA1, VS1, VS2	VA1, VS1, VS2	VA1, VS1, VS2	VA1, VS1, VS2
Service Type	Uplink	Uplink	E2E	Uplink
Ideal Latency	<50ms	<50ms	<15ms	<15ms

Service Interruption	<1s	<30s	<1s	<30s
Bandwidth Requirement	>5Mbps <50Mbps	>5Mbps <50Mbps	<2Mbps	<1Kbps
Device Scenario	Indoor mobile	Indoor stationary	Indoor mobile	Outdoor mobile + Outdoor stationary
Slice Type	eMBB	eMBB	URLLC	IoT
No. Flow	1 per AGV	1 per telemetry station	9 per AGV	2 per device

As shown in table above, each type of use case traffic is identified. According to the description of traffic flow, “HD camera feed (AGV)” refers to a single stream of camera data coming from the AGV, and “HD video screens (Telemetry)” refers to a single stream of camera feed towards the WINGSChariot platform in the cloud.

“Service Type” only describes the main radio service involved for the data flow. Similar to “From/To” info, in practice all data flows require both downlink and uplink radio services. The information here only describes the main radio service type to highlight the boundary and focus of the 5G radio network in different cases. For example, the AGV data is first uploaded from the AGV using the 5G network to the WINGSChariot platform in the cloud and then downloaded to the UE through the corresponding Network Application that manages the AGV operation in the warehouse again using the 5G network. Thus, the URLLC service is defined as end-to-end. For the HD camera feed, in normal situation, the camera data flow is uploaded by 5G network and sent to the WINGSChariot platform in the cloud via fixed network, thus radio service is identified as “Uplink”.

“Ideal Latency” describes the network latency threshold defined by use case owners. Latency for use case traffic is always the lower the better, but the value described here is sufficient to unlock the full potential of the service based on existing use case hardware and software. Note that the value needs to be considered together with “Service Type”.

“Service Interruption” describes the allowed network interruption time of one single traffic stream, NOT the complete traffic type. This is a strong use case dependent value. For example, the allow interruption time of one AGV camera stream is “<1s”, which is required for tele-operation.

“Bandwidth Requirement” is the range of required 5G bandwidth of one data flow.

“Device Scenario” describes the general environment where the 5G UE will be installed. This will have a direct impact of field strength requirement of the 5G signal. “Indoor mobile” refers to 5G UE is normally installed in an indoor environment, and the UE is on mobile which leads to potential handovers or roaming. “Indoor stationary” is similar to “Indoor mobile” while the UE is stationary at a fixed location.

“Slice Type” is a general identification of the type of network slice according to 3GPP standard.

“No.Flow” refers to the number of data flows of the described data flow type of the use case, which leads to the maximum number of flows supported by one 5G device.

6.5.2 Network infrastructure capabilities and site facilities upgrades

As it was described in section 3.3, a 5G SA network will be implemented in Athens for the needs of VITAL-5G UC#3. The network will be able to support features such as slicing and several external monitoring tools will be installed to validate its performance, as seen in Figure 75.

Figure 75: Greek testbed infrastructure

The Greek testbed and facility is upgraded and integrated in the target solution, functional software and hardware components as presented in Figure 48. The components of RAN, Core, Virtualization and orchestration are integrated and installed, offering the E2E functionality of the 5G SA services and slicing, to be consumed by the Network Applications. For clarity, some technical details of the integration steps are provided for slicing, virtualization and orchestration and monitoring, as described in Table 31.

Table 31: Greek testbeds upgraded components

Type	Description
OpenStack (for 5G Core deployment)	OpenStack cloud 352 vCPUs 576 GB RAM 4 TB storage
5G Core SA	5G Core of the Greek testbed
5G RAN	Ericsson BB 6630 and two ERS 4408
5G Network Transport	IP MPLS
5G SA validated devices	Quectel RMU500EK, Nokia Fastmile 5G Gateway, Huawei, HUAWEI 5G Mobile WiFi Pro
5G network monitoring	Network, Service and Infrastructure KPIs
5G network slicing	End to end network slicing available
OpenStack (Virtual Infrastructure for Network Application deployment)	Virtual Infrastructure Manager for VNF Network Apps
OSMv12	Network App orchestrator

Kubernetes	Open-source system for automating deployment, scaling, and management of containerized applications
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Slicing

A slice is a logical 5G network that provides specific network capabilities and network characteristics. A 5GS can provide one or more slice instances of one or more types. A slice type is identified by a S-NSSAI, which is composed of a Slice Service Type, SST, and optionally a Slice Differentiator, SD. Each slice instance is realized by assigning the network functions within each 5G core system to specific S-NSSAI through appropriate configuration. A UE can be allowed to access any number of slices instances in the network. The UPFs provide access to one or more external Data Networks through Data Network Names (DNNS) that are unique within each slice instance while it is possible to provide the same name to access different Data Networks in different slice instances.

The following options are available in the Athens testbed:

- Configure one or more slice per subscriber
- The subscriber can be registered and use one or more slice at the same time
- UPF can be selected on slice base. Different slices can be associated to different UPF.
- One UPF can be dedicated or shared among several slices

The characteristics of each slice are the 5QI values and Allocation and Retention Priority (ARP) that control the QoS forwarding treatment of each flow by the 5G Core and the 5G New Radio. In particular, the 5QI is a scalar value with a one-to-one mapping to a standardized combination of QoS characteristics while ARP defines the relative importance and controls the pre-emption capabilities and vulnerabilities of the QoS flow. In particular, the 5G Core marks the traffic on the N3 interface for downlink and N6 interface on uplink with a DSCP value, in order for the traffic to be suitably treated during its passing through the transport network of the Athens testbed.

Management and Orchestration of operations in the Greek testbed are performed by the Open Source MANO OSM orchestrator (v12).

Figure 76: Greek testbed OSM deployment

Monitoring

As it was described in section 3.3.7, monitoring will be provided by installing monitoring tools that will be able to provide information about:

- Throughput; End-to-end latency; RAN latency
- Packet Loss; Data Rates
- Availability
- Jitter

Figure 77: Greek testbed centralized monitoring platform

6.5.3 Facility Equipment

Autonomous Guided Vehicle (AGV)

After an extensive market search and the acquisition of multiple offers from various robotics manufacturers, the Clearpath Boxer v2.4 indoor robotic platform, was selected as the Autonomous Guided Vehicle (AGV) of choice for the realization of the T&L use case in the Athens trial facility. The key criteria for selecting this specific model were the following:

- Designed for use in indoor manufacturing environments
- Lifting capability of up to 150 Kg, which is more than enough for the pharmaceutical pallets that the DIA warehouse selected contains
- Full ROS1 and ROS2 compatibility which allows for the development of SW and Network Application on top of the factory settings
- Availability of a large variety of onboard sensors, which allow for the precise indoor localization and guidance in complex environments

The Boxer AGV will be retro-fitted with a 5G module to enable communication with the application platform, over the 5G Rel.16 SA testbed that Cosmote will deploy. Additional trolley(s) will be designed and created, to enable the AGV to carry the Euro-pallets available at the DIA warehouse with greater ease. The pallets will be a priori placed on top of the trolley(s) and the Boxer will be able to identify the correct pallet/trolley, navigate under it with high precision, lift it and autonomously move it to the respective designated location(s) within the use case (depending on the use case scenario).

Figure 78: Clearpath Boxer v2.4 AGV to be used in the Athens trials
Boxer full specifications sheet is provided in Annex A.

Environmental Sensor Pack

Besides the AGV, a collection of surrounding fixed sensors and cameras will be mounted in a couple of locations within the warehouse (on the racks/shelves), referred to collectively as the Environmental Sensors pack, as they help monitor the warehouse environment. The pack will be comprised of the following sensors: Temperature sensor; Humidity sensor; Vibration sensor; Luminosity sensor and Full HD USB Camera. All the sensors are packaged together in a rugged casing to protect them and connected to a Raspberry Pi which is used as an aggregation and communication gateway. The Sensor pack is also equipped with a 5G chipset to enable the connection of the environmental sensor pack to the 5G network and the transmission of the sensor and camera data over 5G connectivity, to the VITAL-5G platform.

The data from the environmental sensor pack, will be used to enhance the remote monitoring of the entire warehouse as well as of the AGV's autonomous functionalities, by providing relevant data about the operational environment which may affect the picking/delivery order of products and hence affect the AGV functionalities. Moreover, the mounted camera(s) will provide a wide view of the operational environment and will assist the remote navigation of the AGV (to be provided to the user along with the feed from the on-board camera of the AGV), as well as with its autonomous navigation, as images from the mounted camera may be used to improve the navigational accuracy of the AGV.

In addition to the previously presented end devices, a number of complementary equipment and installations has been planned in order to complete the warehouse upgrade, including a dedicated server room where the RAN equipment will be deployed Figure 79. Obviously, this includes provision and installation of appropriate rack, cables, power supply and automation as well as safety devices and procedures.

Figure 79: Server room – DIA Warehouse

6.5.4 Facility Planning

In this section we present in more details the warehouse areas where the trials will take place together with the respective upgrades and equipment. The trial space is outlined in Table 32.

The demo area (of around 1200 m²) is a specific part of the Warehouse where all the warehouse operations are to take place, as the trials planning for 2022 is presented in Figure 80 and for 2023 is described in Figure 81.

Figure 80: Athens testbed planning 2022

Figure 81: Athens testbed planning 2023

Table 32: Warehouse Planning

Warehouse area	Photo
<p>Inbound/Outbound Ramps – Staging Area</p> <p>Upgrades: 5G connectivity as provided by ERS4408:2</p> <p>Equipment: AGV for autonomous transfer of pallets.</p>	
<p>Corridor from/to the Inbound/Outbound Area</p> <p>Upgrades</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Server installation @Server room • Antenna installation (5G ERS4408:2) <p>Equipment: AGV for autonomous transfer of pallets.</p>	
<p>Picking Area</p> <p>Upgrades: Antenna installation (5G ERS4408:1)</p> <p>Equipment</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • AGV for autonomous transfer of pallets. • AGV for “follow me” function • Environmental Sensors pack. 	
<p>Checking Area</p> <p>Upgrades: Antenna installation (5G ERS4408:1)</p> <p>Equipment</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • AGV for autonomous transfer of pallets. • AGV for “follow me” function • Environmental Sensors pack. 	

7 Mitigation actions of identified risks

The actual status, since **December 2022**, is that the three testbeds have been integrated and are ready to be used for the final experimentation phase of the project. In any case, during the project's activities, we have identified several risks related to the project and to WP3, as we dealt with the 5G infrastructure for all the trial sites, software packages deployments, network infrastructure deployments, equipment's integration and equipment acquisitions. The work regarding the testbeds analysis and required upgrades and extensions is already carried out for the three facilities, even though we took into consideration three main risks that could delay the activities:

- COVID – pandemic context, that can affect the testbeds implementation
- Equipment's acquisition and delivery
- Software/hardware deployment in the testbeds
- Testbeds integration delays

During the pandemic peak, we focused the work for the most demanding activities of architecture design and definition of the required upgrades and testbeds developments, starting also the process of hardware/software acquisition and further proper 5G network integration, as described in the deliverable. We have created the framework of the deployment activities, that could be easily followed by each testbed owner, in relation with the standardization and with project requirements. As per today status, the pandemic is not considered a major issue in all three countries, activities can be performed as planned and there is no impact for the project.

The acquisition of the hardware and software for the required testbeds upgrade was considered as a risk related to the delivery time of the components. The 5G network components, upgrades and integration requirements are well defined in the deliverable, aligned with the Network Application requirements and explained by each of the testbed. Having a clear overview of the components, all the components have been delivered and integrated, for the target architecture implementation.

Even though we have faced some delays in the implementation for the Greek testbed, based on the concentrated effort and planning, the testbed has been 5G SA operational as presented, tested and integrated with the VITAL-5G platform, by December 2022. The risk of delay has been mitigated accordingly, following the design in the reference architecture, benchmarking with the other testbeds for relevant key upgrade actions.

8 Conclusions

In this deliverable we provided the technological implementation of a 5G open testbed, by fulfilling the project's main *Objectives*, but also presenting the E2E network integration steps and activities required for 5G SA Rel.16-compliant testbeds. The results of the activities, integration progress and final validation are already provided, through the experimentation of Network Applications within the 5G SA environment, supporting multi-slice capabilities, as the services are automatically deployed through the relevant orchestration mechanisms.

The technical proposal and 5G testbeds implementation have been aligned with the 5G-PPP architecture, 3GPP standards and other project activities and effort, aligning the general development framework of the testbeds with the SDOs. Also, we have described the state-of-the-art of the testbeds, the existing architecture available in different project phases, the capabilities of the facilities, that gave us the possibility to evaluate the advanced 5G testbeds deployment. The VITAL-5G E2E reference architecture has been provided, along with the design of our technical implementation, network components and software blocks that can facilitate the Network Applications onboarding and testing in the infrastructure. The E2E reference architecture applies to all the testbeds, even if we use different implementations, we can provide to the vertical's use cases owners the same 5G behavior in all three testbeds. We have defined and then implemented the 5G security activities, analysis and technical implementations, in terms of security/cyber security threats and mitigation actions, including an advanced security design of our testbed architecture. We have identified for each of the testbeds the upgrades required to 5G SA Rel.16, all the integration and upgraded steps being performed.

As a conclusion, the deliverable **D3.1 - Report on VITAL-5G infrastructure upgrades & extensions** is aggregating all the information, activities and steps of the VITAL-5G testbed and infrastructure upgrades, network extensions, components integration results providing further outputs for the remaining WP3 deliverables and WP4 activities.

This document can also serve as a 5G E2E design, upgrades and integration activities framework, not only for our testbeds, but for any 5G testbed or 5G MNO or 5G infrastructure facility developer, to perform the 5G services deployments and different use cases, Network Application or other vertical's related experiments.

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Annexes

Annex A: Clearpath Boxer v2.4 – Specification sheet

BOXER™

INDOOR ROBOTIC PLATFORM

SIZE AND WEIGHT	
EXTERNAL DIMENSIONS (L X W X H)	740 X 550 X 309 mm (29.1 X 21.7 X 12.2 in)
WEIGHT	107 kg (236 lb)
SPEED AND PERFORMANCE	
PAYLOAD	150 kg (331 lb)
MAX SPEED / ACCELERATION	2.0 m/s (4.5 mph) / 1.0 m/s ²
SUSPENSION	Fixed
INTEGRATED LIFT	Up to 83 mm (2.44 in) stroke, up to 150 kg capacity
TURNING RADIUS / DRIVE CONFIGURATION	0 mm / Rear-wheel differential drive
MAX GRADE	Up to 1° for typical applications
DOCKING REPEATABILITY - FREE SPACE	Down to ±10 mm positional, ±1° angular; dependent on environment
DOCKING REPEATABILITY - AUTOCHARGE DOCK	Down to ±4 mm lateral, ±10 mm longitudinal, ±0.5° angular; dependent on environment
TEMPERATURE RANGE OPERATION / STORAGE	20 °C to 40 °C (68 °F to 104 °F) / -20 °C to 30 °C (-4 °F to 86 °F)
BATTERY AND POWER SYSTEM	
BATTERY CHEMISTRY / CAPACITY / VOLTAGE	Lithium iron nanophosphate / 924 W-h / 19 - 32 V
USER-FACING POWER INTERFACE	Unregulated, unswitched battery voltage, 12 A maximum
RUNTIME - NAVIGATING / STATIONARY	Approx. 6 hr / Up to 16 hr
CHARGE TIME - AUTODOCK / MANUAL	20 min / 4.5 hr
INTERFACING AND COMMUNICATION	
INTERNAL COMPUTER INTERFACE	ROS2 API
ROS COMPUTER (Optional)	Vecow ECX-2000 series or EVS-2000 series
VISUAL COMMUNICATION	360° LED light pipe for status indication
PAYLOAD INTERFACE	1X Ethernet, RJ-45 female, PoE, 1X USB 3.0a Type A female, 8X Digital inputs, 8X Digital outputs E-stop loop breakout, dual-channel, Serial interface, RS-232, 2-wire, 2X safety relay dry contacts Emergency stop reset interlock
WIFI	802.11 ac/a/b/g/n, 2.4 Ghz, 5 Ghz
SAFETY & NAVIGATION SENSOR	Hokuyo UAM-05LP 2D LiDAR, 270° FoV, 5 m safety-rated protective field range, 20 m non-safety-rated warning field range
REVERSING SENSOR / 3D OBSTACLE SENSOR	Pepper+Fuchs R2100 2D LiDAR, 88° FoV / Intel RealSense D435
DRIVERS / APIs	ROS1 Noetic or ROS2 Foxy, Gazebo, LED Light Control, RViz & URDF Support